

English Translation: Minimum Record Recommendation for Museums and Collections (MDS v1.1)

What is the Minimum Record Recommendation?

Museums and collections want to share the objects in their depots and exhibition spaces with the public and make object information digitally accessible. In addition to presenting their own online collections, there is also the option of taking part in cultural portals.

The [FAIR Principles](#) show how to improve the discoverability, connectivity and reusability of information about collection objects. The use of standards in structuring data, as well as the use of standardised vocabularies and common cataloguing regulations, are of crucial importance here. Especially institutions with limited resources hesitate to meet these supposedly (too) high requirements. The Minimum Record Recommendation shows them where they can start to ensure the sustainability and future viability of their data.

The Minimum Record Recommendation therefore specifies the most important data elements for the online publication of object information from museums and collections and provides information on how these elements should be filled in. The "Minimum Record" is the smallest possible intersection of relevant data elements that ensures a minimum level of data quality across most disciplines and museum types. In-depth cataloguing can build on this if required. The practical implementation of the Recommendation leads to a consistent coverage of the most important data elements for the identification and description of objects, as well as for the most frequently used search criteria.

The [CARE Principles](#) focus on the ethical aspects of publishing cultural heritage data. The cataloguing specifications of the Minimum Record Recommendation refer to the CARE Principles where appropriate. These apply in particular to data on collection items from colonial contexts.

What are the objectives of the Recommendation?

The Minimum Record Recommendation is intended to pave the way for smaller and larger museums and collections to publish their data online and to communicate relevant standards in an easy-to-understand, low-threshold approach. The aim is to raise awareness of data quality in cultural institutions and support them with online publication. The recommendation is intended for practical application in everyday museum work.

The Minimum Record Recommendation is intended to support museums in setting the course for more consistent and higher-quality data right from the start. It assists them in gradually integrating controlled vocabularies into their documentation and publication practice, thus preparing their valuable data sets for up-to-date Linked Open Data scenarios.

Who is behind it?

The Recommendation has been developed by the Minimum Record Working Group. It was initiated in 2022 by the Museum and Media Desks of the German Digital Library (DDB), the Working Group on Digitisation of the Konferenz der Museumsberatungsstellen in den Ländern (KMBL) and digiS Berlin. Members of the working group include representatives from the Institute for Museum Research - Staatliche Museen zu Berlin - Stiftung Preußischer Kulturbesitz, the Fachgruppe Dokumentation of the German Museum Association (DMB), the Coordination Centre for Scientific University Collections in Germany, digiCULT-Verbund eG, museum-digital Deutschland e. V., NFDI4Culture, NFDI4Objects, NFDI4Memory, Museum für Naturkunde Berlin and Übersee-Museum Bremen.

Both during the development of the beta version (2023) and the finalisation of the first full version of the Minimum Record Recommendation, which was published in May 2024, representatives from various stakeholder groups, including museum staff, persons working in consultancy and education, software providers and representatives from various cultural heritage portals, were involved and asked for feedback.

Feedback welcome!

Comments and suggestions for changes are very welcome. They will be considered by the Minimum Record Working Group and may be included in the next version of the Recommendation.

Please send your comments to: info@minimaldatensatz.de

You are welcome to subscribe to our newsletter for useful information and the latest news about the Minimum Record: <https://newsletter.museen-in-bayern.de/f/102943-392139/>

Data element set

Data elements (cataloguing)

Data elements that are usually populated during data entry:

- [Object title or name \(mandatory\)](#)
- [Object type or designation \(mandatory\)](#)
- [Classification \(recommended\)](#)
- [Inventory number \(mandatory\)](#)
- [Object description \(recommended\)](#)
- [Materials \(recommended\)](#)
- [Techniques \(recommended\)](#)
- [Measurements \(recommended\)](#)
- [Event in object history \[element set\] \(mandatory\)](#)

- Event type (mandatory)
- Person/corporate body (conditionally mandatory)
- Date (conditionally mandatory)
- Place (conditionally mandatory)
- Subject keyword (recommended)
- Media file [element set] (mandatory)
 - Link to media file (mandatory)
 - Usage rights of media file (mandatory)
 - Rights holder of media file (conditionally mandatory)
 - Alternative text (recommended)

Data elements (export)

Data fields that are usually populated during or after export from the local database system:

- Record ID (mandatory)
- Record language (mandatory)
- Record type (mandatory)
- Repository of object (mandatory)
- Institution providing record (mandatory)
- Media file: type of media file (mandatory)
- Usage rights of metadata record (mandatory)
- Link to published metadata record (recommended)
- Record date (recommended)

FAQs etc.

- FAQs (English)
- Resources and links
 - Press Release (German): Online-Handreichung zur besseren Auffindbarkeit von Objektinformationen aus Museen veröffentlicht
- Change log (English)
- Credits and citation
 - Acknowledgements

Konferenz der Museumsberatungsstellen in den Ländern

Fachgruppe Dokumentation

Landesstelle für die nichtstaatlichen Museen in Bayern

museum-digital

Data elements (cataloguing)

Data elements that are usually populated during data entry:

- Object title or name (mandatory)
- Object type or designation (mandatory)
- Classification (recommended)
- Inventory number (mandatory)
- Object description (recommended)
- Materials (recommended)
- Techniques (recommended)
- Measurements (recommended)
- Event in object history [element set] (mandatory)
 - Event type (mandatory)
 - Person/corporate body (conditionally mandatory)
 - Date (conditionally mandatory)
 - Place (conditionally mandatory)
- Subject keyword (recommended)
- Media file [element set] (mandatory)
 - Link to media file (mandatory)
 - Usage rights of media file (mandatory)
 - Rights holder of media file (conditionally mandatory)
 - Alternative text (recommended)

Object title or name (mandatory)

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Definition

Unique title or name of the object or work for online presentation

Other possible database element names

Object name

Object proper name

Text/URI

Text

Repeatable

Yes

Obligation level

Mandatory

Recording notes

The object title should describe or identify the object or work as clearly as possible. It should not be identical to the [Object type or designation](#) element. The title may have been given by the creator of the object, or it may be a name commonly used in literature for the individual object. If an object title is not available or known, one can be constructed for online publication. If the object title is composed of multiple data elements, it should be concise and clear to ensure digital accessibility. In such cases, a combination of [Object type or designation](#) with one of the following pieces of information is recommended: [Inventory number](#), [Date](#), or [Technique](#).

The element can be repeated to indicate original titles, alternative titles, etc. In natural history, the scientific name should be used as the object title, with the common name optionally included as an alternative title. Both name or title forms must be supplemented with the [Inventory number](#) to create a unique title for the object.

 CARE: The designation of an collection item from colonial contexts in its country of origin or source community is important for identification and findability. These designations should therefore be included and, where appropriate, prioritised.

Examples

Four Dancing Muses

Four-poster bed, 23971-2

Pamphlet, offset print

Portrait of actress Maria Anna Löhn (1830-1902)

Etruscan lamp with gorgon's head

Minimal polyhedral model of Boy's Surface

Self-propelled sugar beet harvester by Herriau

Monastery complex of the Dominican convent Maria Zuflucht (Weesen)

Frigate "Diana", hull model

Lymnaea stagnalis, ZMA.MOLL.371629

 CARE: Pim toc

Expression in LIDO (v1.0 and v1.1)

```
<lido:objectIdentificationWrap>
  <lido:titleWrap>
    <lido:titleSet lido:type="http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300417200">
      <lido:appellationValue xml:lang="de">Vier tanzende Musen</lido:appellationValue>
      <lido:appellationValue xml:lang="en">Four Dancing Muses</lido:appellationValue>
    </lido:titleSet>
    <lido:titleSet lido:type="http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300417227">
      <lido:appellationValue xml:lang="de">Tanzende Göttinnen</lido:appellationValue>
      <lido:appellationValue xml:lang="en">Dancing Goddesses</lido:appellationValue>
    </lido:titleSet>
  </lido:titleWrap>
</lido:objectIdentificationWrap>
```

Comparison with relevant standards and database models

Standard	Element Name	Text /URI	Repeatable	Obligation level	Comment
German Digital Library: Metadata requirements for data provision	Objekttitel	Text	Yes	Mandatory	
German Digital Library LIDO application profile (DDB-LIDO)	<titleWrap>	Text	Yes	Mandatory	If several titles are provided, they must be labelled so as to make clear which is the preferred title and which are the other titles. In DDB-LIDO, the preferred title in the element <lido:titleSet> is labelled by the type attribute http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300417200 or http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300417205 . Additional titles will be displayed with the label "Other title(s)" or "Original title" and have to be labelled as follows: http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300417227 for "alternate titles" and http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300417204 for "original titles"
CCC-LIDO Application profile	Object title and additional designation for the collection item in the language of origin <titleWrap>	Text	Yes	Mandatory	The title (also known as local name, indigenous name, or proper name) is also recommended and must be typed as follows: "titleLanguageOrigin".
DFG Basic Data Record	Source Object Title	Text	Not specified	Mandatory	
DFG Practical Guidelines on Digitisation: LIDO core metadata	Title/Object name <titleSet>	Text	Yes	Mandatory	
Europeana Data Model (EDM)	<dc:title>	Text	Yes	Conditionally mandatory	In the Europeana Data Model <dc:title> (object title) OR <dc:description> (object description) are mandatory.

EODEM application profile	Title/Name /lido:titleWrap/ lido:titleSet/lido: appellationValue	Text	No	Mandatory	In addition, the <Title_Type> and <Title_Language> elements are mandatory in the EODEM application profile .
Categories for the Description of Works of Art (2024)	3.1. Title Text	Text	Yes	Recommended	CORE element
CDWA Lite (2006)	2.1.1 Title	Text	Yes	Mandatory	If several titles are specified, 2.1 Title Set is repeated.
Spectrum 5.1	Title	Text	Yes	Not specified	The obligation level is determined by the institution.
digiCULT	Titel / Objektname [eng.: Title /Object name]	Text	Yes	Recommended	digiCULT offers the possibility to label the title (descriptive title, original title, etc.) and thus to ensure a distinction between different types of titles.
museum-digital	Object title	Text	Yes	Mandatory	

ID data element

mds0001

Object type or designation (mandatory)

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Definition

The object type is the most specific way of describing what an object or work is, specifying as precisely as possible the type of object to which it belongs.

Other possible database element names

Object name

Factual term

Text/URI

URI (preferred) and/or text (controlled vocabulary)

Repeatable

Yes

Obligation level

Mandatory

Recording notes

The object type indicates what kind of object something is. The term should be taken from a controlled vocabulary. The most specific term in the controlled vocabulary hierarchy should always be used for the object type (as opposed to [Classification](#)). In natural history, the type of taxidermical preparation can be specified in this data element.

 CARE: If the most specific term from the hierarchical ladder of a vocabulary limits the ambiguity of a collection item (e.g. if the indexing institution does not know the meaning in the country of origin and therefore an unambiguous categorisation is not possible), the superordinate term should be selected in this case.

Terminology recommendation

Art & Architecture Thesaurus: [Objects Facet](#)

[Integrated Authority File](#) (GND, German National Library), entity type Subject heading sensu stricto. The following search interfaces provide a convenient way to search the GND: <https://explore.gnd.network/> (GND-Explorer), <https://lobid.org/gnd> (lobid-gnd), <https://swb.bsz-bw.de/DB=2.104/> (OGND)

[Wikidata](#)

[Objektbezeichnungsdatei](#) (For the Object type, the third and possibly the second hierarchy level are particularly suitable.)

Examples

URI	Preferred term
http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300312262	statuettes (free-standing sculpture)
http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300041402	wood engravings (prints)
http://obg.vocnet.org/obg00652	Flugschrift [eng.: Pamphlet]
http://obg.vocnet.org/obg00982	Fotoabzug [eng.: Photographic print]
https://d-nb.info/gnd/4599991-0	Himmelbett [eng.: Canopy bed]
http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300046012	rings (finger jewelry)
https://d-nb.info/gnd/4535319-0	Dermoplastik (Tierpräparat) [eng.: Taxidermy mount]
http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300199921	bread knives
http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300198948	springform pans
https://d-nb.info/gnd/4208226-2	Leuchtpistole [eng.: flare pistol]
http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q12760	steam engine
http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300007466	churches (buildings)
http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q73419810	counterfeit coin

Expression in LIDO v1.0

```
<lido:objectWorkTypeWrap>
  <lido:objectWorkType>
    <lido:conceptID lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00099">http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300199921</lido:conceptID>
    <lido:term xml:lang="de">Brotmesser</lido:term>
    <lido:term xml:lang="en">bread knives</lido:term>
  </lido:objectWorkType>
</lido:objectWorkTypeWrap>
```

Expression in LIDO v1.1

```
<lido:objectWorkTypeWrap>
  <lido:objectWorkType>
    <skos:Concept rdf:about="http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300199921">
      <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="de">Brotmesser</skos:prefLabel>
      <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="en">bread knives</skos:prefLabel>
    </skos:Concept>
  </lido:objectWorkType>
</lido:objectWorkTypeWrap>
```

Comparison with relevant standards and database models

Standard	Element name	Text /URI	Repeatable	Obligation level	Comment
German Digital Library: Metadata requirements for data provision	Objektyp	Text (controlled vocabulary) and URI	Yes	Mandatory	
German Digital Library LIDO application profile (DDB-LIDO)	<objectWorkType>	Text (controlled vocabulary) and URI	Yes	Mandatory	

CCC-LIDO Application profile	Objekt type <objectWorkType>	Text (controlled vocabulary) and URI	Yes	Mandatory	Only values from controlled vocabularies (AAT, Wikidata, GND) are transferred to the "Object type" search filter.
DFG Basic Data Record	Source Object Type	Text (controlled vocabulary) and URI	Not specified	Mandatory	
DFG Practical Guidelines on Digitisation: LIDO core metadata	Object or work type <objectWorkType>	Text (controlled vocabulary) and URI	Yes	Mandatory	
Europeana Data Model (EDM)	<dc:type>	Text (controlled vocabulary) and URI	Yes	Conditionally mandatory	In the Europeana Data Model <dc:subject> (subject keyword /classification) OR <dc:type> (object type) OR <dcterms:spatial> (keyword [place/location depicted/represented]) OR <dcterms:temporal>(keyword [time depicted/as subject]) are mandatory.
EODEM Application profile	Object Type Identifier; Object Type Keyword /lido: objectWorkTypeWrap /lido:objectWorkType/lido: conceptID and /lido:term	Text (controlled vocabulary) and URI	Yes	Mandatory	
Categories for the Description of Works of Art (2024)	1.2 Object/Work Type	Text (controlled vocabulary) and URI	Yes	Recommended	CORE element Vocabulary recommendation: Art & Architecture Thesaurus or general terms in another controlled vocabulary.
CDWA Lite (2006)	1.1 Object/Work Type	Text (controlled vocabulary) and URI	Yes	Mandatory	Vocabulary recommendation: Art & Architecture Thesaurus
Spectrum 5.1	Object name	Text (controlled vocabulary)	Yes	Recommended	Core element The obligation level is determined by the institution.
digiCULT	Objektbezeichnung [eng.: Object designation]	Text (controlled vocabulary) and URI	Yes	Recommended	
museum-digital	Object type	Text (controlled vocabulary) and URI	Yes	Mandatory	

ID data element

mds0002

Classification (recommended)

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Definition

Assignment of the object or work to a classification or other vocabulary that groups similar objects on the basis of defined characteristics

Other possible database element names

Subject group

Functional classification

Subject classification

Object category

Category

Higher taxonomy

Taxon

Denomination / Weight standard

Text/URI

Text (controlled vocabulary) and/or URI

Repeatable

Yes

Obligation level

Recommended

Recording notes

This data element assigns the cultural heritage object to a larger systematic or thematic grouping. Taxonomic information for objects in natural history collections may also be recorded in this data element. It is sufficient to indicate the most specific hierarchical level of a classification. Higher levels should not be recorded.

Information on a [local classification](#) (e.g. collection / sub-collection) is desirable when cataloguing. But these are not an integral part of the Minimum Record Recommendation.

 CARE: The assignment to a classification should not limit the ambiguity of a collection item. In order to make the historical context of the data production transparent, the classification information in an event in the object history "[Type assignment](#)" is suitable. Alternative vocabularies are helpful to mitigate the Eurocentric perspective (see terminology recommendation).

Terminology recommendation

Dewey Decimal Classification: [DDC subject classes](#)

[Integrated Authority File](#) (GND, German National Library): [GND Subject Categories](#) und [GND Subject headings sensu stricto](#). The following search interfaces provide a convenient way to search the GND: <https://explore.gnd.network/> (GND-Explorer), <https://lobid.org/gnd> (lobid-gnd), <https://swb.bsz-bw.de/DB=2.104/> (OGND)

[Hessische Systematik](#) (see also [this service](#))

[Catalogue of Life](#) for natural history objects

 [CARE: Brian Deer Classification System \(BDC\)](#) for the representation of indigenous knowledge

Examples

URI	Preferred term
https://d-nb.info/standards/vocab/gnd/gnd-sc#32.1*	Agriculture (misc.), history of agriculture
https://d-nb.info/standards/vocab/gnd/gnd-sc#17.3	Material culture, folk art
https://d-nb.info/gnd/4123307-4	Grabbeigabe [eng: Grave goods <LCSH match>]
http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300191372	drachmas
https://www.catalogueoflife.org/data/taxon/BMGVD	Mammalia
https://d-nb.info/gnd/4741325-6	Aspleniaceae (preferred term GND: Streifenfarngewächse)

Expression in LIDO v1.0

```
<lido:objectClassificationWrap>
  <lido:classificationWrap>
    <lido:classification lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00932">
      <lido:conceptID lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00099">https://d-nb.
info/gnd/4034402-2</lido:conceptID>
      <lido:term xml:lang="de">Landwirtschaft</lido:term>
      <lido:term xml:lang="en">agriculture (discipline)</lido:term>
    </lido:classification>
  </lido:classificationWrap>
</lido:objectClassificationWrap>
```

```
<lido:objectClassificationWrap>
  <lido:classificationWrap>
    <lido:classification lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido01144">
      <lido:conceptID lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00099">https://www.
catalogueoflife.org/data/taxon/652YZ</lido:conceptID>
      <lido:term lido:label="Gattung/Art">Addax nasomaculatus</lido:term>
    </lido:classification>
  </lido:classificationWrap>
</lido:objectClassificationWrap>
```

Expression in LIDO v1.1

```

<lido:objectClassificationWrap>
  <lido:classificationWrap>
    <lido:classification lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00932">
      <skos:Concept rdf:about="//d-nb.info/gnd/4034402-2">
        <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="de">Landwirtschaft</skos:prefLabel>
        <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="en">agriculture (discipline)</skos:
prefLabel>
      </skos:Concept>
    </lido:classification>
  </lido:classificationWrap>
</lido:objectClassificationWrap>

```

```

<lido:objectClassificationWrap>
  <lido:classificationWrap>
    <lido:classification lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido01144">
      <skos:Concept rdf:about="https://www.catalogueoflife.org/data/taxon/652YZ">
        <skos:prefLabel>Addax nasomaculatus</skos:prefLabel>
      </skos:Concept>
    </lido:classification>
  </lido:classificationWrap>
</lido:objectClassificationWrap>

```

Comparison with relevant standards and database models

Standard	Element name	Text/URI	Repeatable	Obligation level	Comment
German Digital Library: Metadata requirements for data provision	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	
German Digital Library LIDO application profile (DDB-LIDO)	<classification>	Text (controlled vocabulary) and optional URI	Yes	Recommended	
CCC-LIDO Application profile	Object genre <classification>	Text and optional URI	Yes	Recommended	The designation for natural history collection items must be typified as follows: " http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido01144 " or "Special classification".
DFG Basic Data Record	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	
DFG Practical Guidelines on Digitisation: LIDO core metadata	Classification <classification>	Text (controlled vocabulary) and/or URI	Yes	Recommended	
Europeana Data Model (EDM)	<dc:subject>	Text (controlled vocabulary) and/or URI	Yes	Conditionally mandatory	In the Europeana Data Model <dc:subject> (subject keyword/classification) OR <dc:type> (object type) OR <dcterms:spatial> (keyword [place/location depicted/represented]) OR <dcterms:temporal>(keyword [time depicted/as subject]) are mandatory.
EODEM application profile	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	
Categories for the Description of Works of Art (2024)	2.1. Classification Term	Text (controlled vocabulary)	Yes	Recommended	CORE element Vocabulary recommendation: Art & Architecture Thesaurus or general terms in another controlled vocabulary.
CDWA Lite (2006)	16.1 Classification	Text (controlled vocabulary)	Yes	Not mandatory	
Spectrum 5.1	Object name with Object name level	Text (controlled vocabulary)	Yes	Not specified	The obligation level is determined by the institution.

digiCULT	Sachgruppe [eng.: Subject group]	Text (controlled vocabulary) and/or URI	Yes	Recommend ed	
museum-digital	(No direct match) (Schlagwort or Bezug)	Text (controlled vocabulary) and/or URI	Yes	Not applicable	Museum-digital does not make a distinction between "keyword" and "subject category", contrary to the Minimum Record Recommendation.

ID data element

mds0003

Inventory number (mandatory)

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Definition

Unique (alpha)numeric identification number of the object, assigned by the institution holding the object, which serves as proof of ownership

Other possible database element names

Identification number

Old inventory number

Object number

Item number

Signature

Catalog number

Lost Art-ID

Other numbers, e. g. plaster cast number, excavation number, find location number ...

Text/URI

Text

Repeatable

Yes (former inventory number, or the like)

Obligation level

Mandatory

Recording notes

This data element contains the current unique identification number for the object within the museum or collection.

Examples

EX 000 230

VIIIa Coll 599

Arch 23971-2

I/09208/00

Expression in LIDO (v1.0 and v1.1)

```
<lido:respositoryWrap>
  <lido:repositorySet lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00475">
    <lido:workID lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00113">EX 000 230</lido:workID>
  </lido:repositorySet>
</lido:respositoryWrap>
```

Comparison with relevant standards and database models

Standard	Element name	Text /URI	Repeatable	Obligation level	Comment
German Digital Library: Metadata requirements for data provision	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	
German Digital Library LIDO application profile (DDB-LIDO)	<repositorySet> / <workID>	Text	Yes	Not mandatory	If several inventory numbers are supplied for an object/work (e.g. current and old inventory numbers), these should be typified. This can be done in LIDO using the type attribute of <workID>.
CCC-LIDO Application profile	Inventory number <repositorySet> / <workID>	Text	Yes	Not mandatory	
DFG Basic Data Record	Source Object Identifier (ID)	URI	Not specified	Mandatory	The DFG Basic Data Record allows the assignment of a unique, global and long-term identifier for the analogue source object.
DFG Practical Guidelines on Digitisation: LIDO core metadata	Repository /location: <repositorySet> / <workID>	Text	Yes	Mandatory, if available	
Europeana Data Model (EDM)	<dc:identifier>	Text	Yes	Recommended	
EODEM application profile	Object Identifier /lido: respositoryWrap /lido:repositorySet /lido:workID	Text	No	Mandatory	
Categories for the Description of Works of Art (2024)	21.2.3. Repository Numbers	Text	Yes	Recommended	CORE element In 21.2.3.1. Number Type, a typification is recommended, e.g. accession number, shelf number, object identifier or inventory number.
CDWA Lite (2006)	14.1.2 Repository Work Identification Number	Text	Yes	Recommended	
Spectrum 5.1	Object number	Text	No	Recommended	Core element for inventory number, For different kinds of numbers use the element "other number".
digiCULT	Inventarnummer [eng.: Inventory number]	Text	Yes	Recommended	The inventory number can either be entered manually in digiCULT or it can be assigned automatically by the system according to a pre-defined scheme.
museum-digital	Inventory number	Text	Yes	Mandatory	In museum-digital, a suggestion for the inventory number can be generated automatically by the system. A consistency check is also performed to avoid duplication of inventory numbers. See also https://de.handbook.museum-digital.info/ .

ID data element

mds0004

Object description (recommended)

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- [ID data element](#)

Definition

Textual description of the object or work

Other possible database element names

Description

Text/URI

Text

Repeatable

Yes

Obligation level

Recommended

(museum-digital: Mandatory)

Recording notes

The object description should describe the object or work briefly and concisely. It should be written in a way that requires as little prior knowledge as possible and is understandable to a wide audience. The object description should contain as many relevant keywords as possible to make it easier to find the object record in a free text search. If the object description text is subject to special usage rights (e.g. copyright), this should be indicated in a separate data element (in LIDO: `<lido:objectDescriptionRights>`, from LIDO v1.1).

AI writing assistants can be used to generate inclusive description texts. However, the result should always be checked by an editor and amended if necessary.

Examples

The façade architecture of the cabinet is modelled on ancient theatres. With its ingenious system of compartments and drawers, it was used to store the treasures collected in the *Kunstkammer*. As well as being functional furniture, the cabinet itself is also a work of art. The ivory panels show extensive imagery: the founders of the four great empires of Antiquity and the deeds of the virtuous ancient hero Hercules. The pull-out writing tablet contains a rotatable world map that refers to the Habsburgs and suggests that the cabinet was made for King Phillip II of Spain.

Expression in LIDO v1.0

```

<lido:objectDescriptionWrap>
  <lido:objectDescriptionSet>
    <lido:descriptiveNoteValue xml:lang="de">Die Fassadenarchitektur des Kabinettschranks findet ihr Vorbild im antiken Theaterbau. Mit seinem ausgeklügelten System von Fächern und Schubladen diente er zur Aufbewahrung von gesammelten Kostbarkeiten der Kunstkammer. Über seine Bestimmung zum funktionalen Möbel hinaus ist der Schrank selbst auch als Kunstwerk zu verstehen. Die Elfenbeintafeln zeigen ein umfangreiches Bildprogramm: die Gründer der vier großen Weltreiche des Altertums und die Taten des tugendhaften antiken Helden Herkules. Die ausziehbare Schreibplatte enthält eine drehbare Weltkarte, die auf die Habsburger verweist und vermuten lässt, dass das Kabinettmöbel für König Phillip II. von Spanien angefertigt worden ist.</lido:descriptiveNoteValue>
    <lido:descriptiveNoteValue xml:lang="en">The façade architecture of the cabinet is modelled on ancient theatres. With its ingenious system of compartments and drawers, it was used to store the treasures collected in the Kunstkammer. As well as being functional furniture, the cabinet itself is also a work of art. The ivory panels show extensive imagery: the founders of the four great empires of Antiquity and the deeds of the virtuous ancient hero Hercules. The pull-out writing tablet contains a rotatable world map that refers to the Habsburgs and suggests that the cabinet was made for King Phillip II of Spain.</lido:descriptiveNoteValue>
  </lido:objectDescriptionSet>
</lido:objectDescriptionWrap>

```

Expression in LIDO v1.1

(Including <lido:objectDescriptionRights>)

```

<lido:objectDescriptionWrap>
  <lido:objectDescriptionSet>
    <lido:descriptiveNoteValue xml:lang="de">Die Fassadenarchitektur des Kabinettschranks findet ihr Vorbild im antiken Theaterbau. Mit seinem ausgeklügelten System von Fächern und Schubladen diente er zur Aufbewahrung von gesammelten Kostbarkeiten der Kunstkammer. Über seine Bestimmung zum funktionalen Möbel hinaus ist der Schrank selbst auch als Kunstwerk zu verstehen. Die Elfenbeintafeln zeigen ein umfangreiches Bildprogramm: die Gründer der vier großen Weltreiche des Altertums und die Taten des tugendhaften antiken Helden Herkules. Die ausziehbare Schreibplatte enthält eine drehbare Weltkarte, die auf die Habsburger verweist und vermuten lässt, dass das Kabinettmöbel für König Phillip II. von Spanien angefertigt worden ist.</lido:descriptiveNoteValue>
    <lido:descriptiveNoteValue xml:lang="en">The façade architecture of the cabinet is modelled on ancient theatres. With its ingenious system of compartments and drawers, it was used to store the treasures collected in the Kunstkammer. As well as being functional furniture, the cabinet itself is also a work of art. The ivory panels show extensive imagery: the founders of the four great empires of Antiquity and the deeds of the virtuous ancient hero Hercules. The pull-out writing tablet contains a rotatable world map that refers to the Habsburgs and suggests that the cabinet was made for King Phillip II of Spain.</lido:descriptiveNoteValue>
    <lido:objectDescriptionRights>
      <lido:rightsType>
        <skos:Concept rdf:about="http://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/">
          <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="de">CC0 1.0 Universell</skos:prefLabel>
          <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="en">CC0 1.0 Universal</skos:prefLabel>
        </skos:Concept>
      </lido:rightsType>
    </lido:objectDescriptionRights>
  </lido:objectDescriptionSet>
</lido:objectDescriptionWrap>

```

Comparison with relevant standards and database models

Standard	Element name	Text /URI	Repeatable	Obligation level	Comment
German Digital Library: Metadata requirements for data provision	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	
German Digital Library LIDO application profile (DDB-LIDO)	<objectDescriptionSet> </descriptiveNoteValue>	Text	Yes	Conditionally mandatory Recommended	Mandatory if sub-elements exist.

CCC-LIDO Application profile	Description <objectDescriptionSet> </descriptiveNoteValue>	Text	Yes	Recommended	
DFG Basic Data Record	Source Object Description	URI	Not specified	Recommended	
DFG Practical Guidelines on Digitisation: LIDO core metadata	Object description <objectDescriptionSet>	Text and/or URI	Yes	Recommended	
Europeana Data Model (EDM)	<dc:description>	Text	Yes	Conditionally mandatory	In Europeana Data Model <dc:title> (Object title) OR <dc:description> (Object description) are mandatory.
EODEM application profile	Brief Description /lido:objectDescriptionWrap /lido:objectDescriptionSet/ lido:descriptiveNoteValue		No	Recommended	
Categories for the Description of Works of Art (2024)	18.1. Descriptive Note Text	Text	No	Not mandatory	Additional elements are recommended to describe specific aspects: Abstract Description, Pagination Description, Foliation Description, Extent Description, Arrangement Description.
CDWA Lite (2006)	17.1 Description/Descriptive Note Set	Text	Yes	Not mandatory	
Spectrum 5.1	Brief description Physical description	Text	No	Recommended	"Brief description" is a core element. The obligation level is determined by the institution.
digiCULT	Beschreibung [eng.: Description]	Text	Yes	Recommended	In digiCULT, for legal reasons, when data is made available via the OAI interface, the description is not included by default.
museum-digital	Description	Text	No	Mandatory	In museum-digital the object description is mandatory. The text has a minimum length of 25 characters.

ID data element

mds0005

Materials (recommended)

Contents

- [Definition](#)
- [Text/URI](#)
- [Repeatable](#)
- [Obligation level](#)
- [Recording notes](#)
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- [Examples](#)
- [Expression in LIDO v1.0](#)
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- [ID data element](#)

Definition

An indication of the materials from which an object or work is made

Text/URI

Text (controlled vocabulary) and/or URI

Repeatable

Yes

Obligation level

Recommended

Recording notes

This data element indicates the materials from which the object or work was or is made or is composed of. Controlled vocabulary is recommended. This supports better findability in portals.

Terminology recommendation

Art & Architecture Thesaurus: [Materials Facet](#)

[Integrated Authority File](#) (GND, German National Library): The following search interfaces provide a convenient way to search the GND: <https://explore.gnd.network/> (GND-Explorer), <https://lobid.org/gnd> (lobid-gnd), <https://swb.bsz-bw.de/DB=2.104/> (OGND)

[Wikidata](#)

Examples

URI	Preferred term
http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300011029	silver (metal)
https://d-nb.info/gnd/4350482-6	Bast [engl.: Bast]
https://d-nb.info/gnd/4144643-4	Bergkristall [engl.: Rock crystal]
https://d-nb.info/gnd/4152058-0	Email (Beschichtung) [eng: Enamel and enameling <LCSH match>]
https://d-nb.info/gnd/4033676-1	Kunststoff [eng: Plastics <LCSH match>]
http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300015062	tempera
http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q28129555	zinc sheet

<https://d-nb.info/gnd/118728372X>

Elektron (Legierung) [eng: Elektrum <LCSH match>]

Expression in LIDO v1.0

```
<lido:eventMaterialsTech>
  <lido:materialsTech>
    <lido:termMaterialsTech lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00132">
      <lido:conceptID lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00099">http://vocab.
getty.edu/aat/300011029</lido:conceptID>
      <lido:term xml:lang="de">Silber</lido:term>
      <lido:term xml:lang="en">silver (metal)</lido:term>
    </lido:termMaterialsTech>
  </lido:materialsTech>
</lido:eventMaterialsTech>
```

Expression in LIDO v1.1

```
<lido:eventMaterialsTech>
  <lido:materialsTech>
    <lido:termMaterialsTech type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00132">
      <skos:Concept rdf:about="http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300011029">
        <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="de">Silber</skos:prefLabel>
        <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="en">silver (metal)</skos:prefLabel>
      </skos:Concept>
    </lido:termMaterialsTech>
  </lido:materialsTech>
</lido:eventMaterialsTech>
```

Example of an event-independent materials specification

```
<lido:objectMaterialsTechWrap>
  <lido:objectMaterialsTechSet>
    <lido:materialsTech>
      <lido:termMaterialsTech lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00132">
        <skos:Concept rdf:about="http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300011029">
          <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="de">Silber</skos:prefLabel>
          <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="en">silver (metal)</skos:prefLabel>
        </skos:Concept>
      </lido:termMaterialsTech>
    </lido:materialsTech>
  </lido:objectMaterialsTechSet>
</lido:objectMaterialsTechWrap>
```

Comparison with relevant standards and database models

Standard	Element name	Text/URI	Repeatable	Obligation level	Comment
German Digital Library: Metadata requirements for data provision	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not mandatory	
German Digital Library LIDO application profile (DDB-LIDO)	<eventMaterialsTech> / <materialsTech> / <termMaterialsTech> / <term>	Text (controlled vocabulary) and optional URI	Yes	Not mandatory	Optional labelling: http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00132 for Materials
CCC-LIDO Application profile	Material/Technique <eventMaterialsTech> / <materialsTech> / <termMaterialsTech> / <term> and <conceptID>	Text (controlled vocabulary) and optional URI (AAT)	Yes	Not mandatory	

DFG Basic Data Record	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not mandatory	
DFG Practical Guidelines on Digitisation: LIDO core metadata	Information on materials and techniques relating to event <eventMaterialsTech>	Text (controlled vocabulary) and /or URI	Yes	Mandatory if available	Alternatively, the information on material and/or technology in <objectMaterialsTechWrap> / <objectMaterialsTechSet> is also possible independently of the event.
Europeana Data Model (EDM)	<dcterms:medium>	Text (controlled vocabulary)	Yes	Not mandatory	
EODEM application profile	Material Description /lido:objectMaterialsTechWrap /lido:objectMaterialsTechSet/ lido:displayMaterialsTech/	Text	Yes	Recommended	
Categories for the Description of Works of Art (2024)	7.5 Materials/Techniques Name	Text (controlled vocabulary)	Yes	Recommended	7.1. Materials/Techniques Description is listed as CORE-Element. Vocabulary recommendation: Art & Architecture Thesaurus or general terms in another controlled vocabulary.
CDWA Lite (2006)	8.1.1 Term Materials Techniques	Text (controlled vocabulary)	Yes	Not mandatory	Vocabulary recommendation: Art & Architecture Thesaurus .
Spectrum 5.1	Material	Text (controlled vocabulary)	Yes	Not specified	The obligation level is determined by the institution.
digiCULT	Material [eng.: Materials]	Text (controlled vocabulary) and /or URI	Yes	Recommended	
museum-digital	Materials/Technique Materials Schlagwort (Material) [eng.: tags (material)]	Text	Yes	Recommended	Materials and techniques can be recorded in museum-digital in different ways: Either in one or in two separate data fields; recently it has also become possible to record them as a "categorised keyword". See this blog post .

ID data element

mds0006

Techniques (recommended)

Contents

- [Definition](#)
- [Other possible database element names](#)
- [Text/URI](#)
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- [Comparison with relevant standards and database models](#)
- [ID data element](#)

Definition

Indication of the technique used in the production, preparation or preservation/storage of the object or work

Other possible database element names

Production technique

Type of preparation

Type of storage

Text/URI

Text (controlled vocabulary) and/or URI

Repeatable

Yes

Obligation level

Recommended

Recording notes

This data element indicates the techniques with which the object was produced, prepared or preserved/stored. Controlled vocabulary is recommended. This supports better findability in portals.

Terminology recommendation

Art & Architecture Thesaurus: Activities Facet, hierarchy name: [Processes and Techniques](#)

[Integrated Authority File](#) (GND, German National Library): The following search interfaces provide a convenient way to search the GND: <https://explore.gnd.network/> (GND-Explorer), <https://lobid.org/gnd> (lobid-gnd), <https://swb.bsz-bw.de/DB=2.104/> (OGND)

[Wikidata](#)

Examples

URI	Vorzugsbezeichnung
https://d-nb.info/gnd/4133335-4	Offsetdruck [eng: Offset printing <LCSH match>]

http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300206846	striking (metalworking)
http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300053418	heightening
http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300053242	aquatint (printing process)
https://d-nb.info/gnd/4012912-3	Drehseln [eng: Turning (Lathe work) <LCSH match>]
https://d-nb.info/gnd/4153775-0	Fassmalerei [eng: Polychromy <LCSH match>]
http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q1259197	wood engraving technique
http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300053991	plating (metal coating)
http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300053400	priming (coating process)
https://d-nb.info/gnd/7511674-1	Tierpräparation [eng.: Taxidermy]

Expression in LIDO v1.0

```
<lido:eventMaterialsTech>
  <lido:materialsTech>
    <lido:termMaterialsTech lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00131">
      <lido:conceptID lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00099">https://d-nb.info/gnd/4133335-4</lido:conceptID>
      <lido:term xml:lang="de">Offsetdruck</lido:term>
      <lido:term xml:lang="en">offset printing</lido:term>
    </lido:termMaterialsTech>
  </lido:materialsTech>
</lido:eventMaterialsTech>
```

Expression in LIDO v1.1

```
<lido:eventMaterialsTech>
  <lido:materialsTech>
    <lido:termMaterialsTech lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00131">
      <skos:Concept rdf:about="https://d-nb.info/gnd/4133335-4">
        <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="de">Offsetdruck</skos:prefLabel>
        <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="en">offset printing</skos:prefLabel>
      </skos:Concept>
    </lido:termMaterialsTech>
  </lido:materialsTech>
</lido:eventMaterialsTech>
```

Example of an event-independent technique

```
<lido:objectMaterialsTechWrap>
  <lido:objectMaterialsTechSet>
    <lido:materialsTech>
      <lido:termMaterialsTech lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00131">
        <skos:Concept rdf:about="https://d-nb.info/gnd/4133335-4">
          <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="de">Offsetdruck</skos:prefLabel>
          <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="en">offset printing</skos:prefLabel>
        </skos:Concept>
      </lido:termMaterialsTech>
    </lido:materialsTech>
  </lido:objectMaterialsTechSet>
</lido:objectMaterialsTechWrap>
```

Comparison with relevant standards and database models

Standard	Element name	Text/URI	Repeatable	Obligation level	Comment
----------	--------------	----------	------------	------------------	---------

German Digital Library: Metadata requirements for data provision	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	
German Digital Library LIDO application profile (DDB-LIDO)	<eventMaterialsTech> / <materialsTech> / <termMaterialsTech> / <term>	Text (controlled vocabulary) and optional URI	Yes	Not mandatory	Optional labelling: http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00131 for Techniques
CCC-LIDO Application profile	Material/Techniques <eventMaterialsTech> / <materialsTech> / <termMaterialsTech> / <term> und <conceptID>	Text (controlled vocabulary) and optional URI (AAT)	Yes	Not mandatory	
DFG Basic Data Record	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not mandatory	
DFG Practical Guidelines on Digitisation: LIDO core metadata	Information on materials and techniques relating to event <eventMaterialsTech>	Text (controlled vocabulary) and /or URI	Yes	Mandatory if available	Alternatively, the information on material and/or technology in <objectMaterialsTechWrap> / <objectMaterialsTechSet> is also possible independently of the event.
Europeana Data Model (EDM)	<dcterms:medium>	Text (controlled vocabulary)	Yes	Not mandatory	
EODEM application profile	Material Description /lido:objectMaterialsTechWrap /lido:objectMaterialsTechSet/ lido:displayMaterialsTech/	Text	Yes	Recommended	
Categories for the Description of Works of Art (2024)	7.5 Materials/Techniques Name	Text (controlled vocabulary)	Yes	Recommended	7.1. Materials/Techniques Description is listed as CORE-Element. Vocabulary recommendation: Art & Architecture Thesaurus or general terms in another controlled vocabulary.
CDWA Lite (2006)	8.1.1 Term Materials Techniques	Text (controlled vocabulary)	Yes	Not mandatory	Vocabulary recommendation: Art & Architecture Thesaurus .
Spectrum 5.1	Technique	Text (controlled vocabulary)	Yes	Not specified	The obligation level is determined by the institution.
digiCULT	Technik [engl.: Technique]	Text (controlled vocabulary) and /or URI	Yes	Recommended	
museum-digital	Materials/Technique Technique Keyword (technique)	Text	Yes	Recommended	Materials and techniques can be recorded in museum-digital in different ways: Either in one or in two separate data fields; recently it has also become possible to record them as a "categorised keyword". See this blog post .

ID data element

mds0007

Measurements (recommended)

Contents

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Definition

Information on the dimensions of an object or work

Other possible database element names

Dimensions

Measurements and dimensions

Measurement data

Text/URI

Text (numeric) with use of controlled values for measurement type and measurement unit

Repeatable

Yes

Obligation level

Recommended

Recording notes

These data elements are used to record measurements for the object or work. The numerical value, measurement type (e.g. weight) and unit of measurement (e.g. kg) are each recorded in a separate data element. Controlled values are recommended for the measurement type (e.g. weight) and unit of measurement (e.g. kg).

Terminology recommendations

(For measurement type and unit of measurement)

Art & Architecture Thesaurus: [Physical Attributes Facet](#), hierarchy name: [Size / Dimensions](#)

[Wikidata](#)

Examples

Height: 2,1 cm

Weight: 50,9 g

Diameter: 32,5 mm

Stamp position: 12 h

Expression in LIDO v1.0

```
<lido:objectMeasurementsWrap>
  <lido:objectMeasurementsSet>
    <lido:objectMeasurements>
      <lido:measurementsSet>
        <lido:measurementType xml:lang="de">Höhe</lido:measurementType>
        <lido:measurementType xml:lang="en">height</lido:measurementType>
        <lido:measurementUnit>cm</lido:measurementUnit>
        <lido:measurementValue>2,1</lido:measurementValue>
      </lido:measurementsSet>
    </lido:objectMeasurements>
  </lido:objectMeasurementsSet>
</lido:objectMeasurementsWrap>
```

Expression in LIDO v1.1

```
<lido:objectMeasurementsWrap>
  <lido:objectMeasurementsSet>
    <lido:objectMeasurements>
      <lido:measurementsSet>
        <lido:measurementType>
          <skos:Concept rdf:about="https://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q208826">
            <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="en">height</skos:prefLabel>
            <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="de">Höhe</skos:prefLabel>
          </skos:Concept>
        </lido:measurementType>
        <lido:measurementUnit>
          <skos:Concept rdf:about="https://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q174728">
            <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="en">centimetre</skos:prefLabel>
            <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="de">Zentimeter</skos:prefLabel>
          </skos:Concept>
        </lido:measurementUnit>
        <lido:measurementValue>2,1</lido:measurementValue>
      </lido:measurementsSet>
    </lido:objectMeasurements>
  </lido:objectMeasurementsSet>
</lido:objectMeasurementsWrap>
```

Example of an event-dependent measurement specification

```

<lido:eventWrap>
  <lido:eventSet>
    <lido:event>
      <lido:eventObjectMeasurements>
        <lido:objectMeasurements>
          <lido:measurementsSet>
            <lido:measurementType>
              <skos:Concept rdf:about="https://www.wikidata.org/entity
/Q208826">
                <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="en">height</skos:prefLabel>
                <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="de">Höhe</skos:prefLabel>
              </skos:Concept>
            </lido:measurementType>
            <lido:measurementUnit>
              <skos:Concept rdf:about="https://www.wikidata.org/entity
/Q174728">
                <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="en">centimetre</skos:
prefLabel>
                <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="de">Zentimeter</skos:
prefLabel>
              </skos:Concept>
            </lido:measurementUnit>
            <lido:measurementValue>2,1</lido:measurementValue>
          </lido:measurementsSet>
        </lido:objectMeasurements>
      </lido:eventObjectMeasurements>
    </lido:event>
  </lido:eventSet>
</lido:eventWrap>

```

Comparison with relevant standards and database models

Standard	Element name	Text/URI	Repeatable	Obligation level	Comment
German Digital Library: Metadata requirements for data provision	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	
German Digital Library LIDO application profile (DDB-LIDO)	<objectMeasurement sWrap>	Text	Yes	Conditionally mandatory	Mandatory if sub-elements exist.
CCC-LIDO Application profile	Dimensions <objectMeasurement sWrap>	Text	Yes	Conditionally mandatory	In the CCC-Lido Application profile, URIs (AAT) are only evaluated for <extentMeasurements>.
DFG Basic Data Record	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not mandatory	
DFG Practical Guidelines on Digitisation: LIDO core metadata	Measurements <objectMeasurement sSet>	Text	Yes	Mandatory if available	In the DFG Practical Guidelines on Digitisation <displayObjectMeasurements> is mandatory; structured information in <objectMeasurements> / <measurementsSet> is additionally recommended.
Europeana Data Model (EDM)	<dcterms:extent>	Text and/or URI	Yes	Not mandatory	
EODEM application profile	Measurement Group /lido:objectMeasurements Wrap/lido:objectMeasurements Set	Text	Yes	Recommended	
Categories for the Description of Works of Art (2024)	6.2. Dimensions Type 6.3. Dimensions Value 6.4. Dimensions Unit	Text (controlled values, controlled format)	Yes	Recommended	6.1. Dimensions Description ist listed as CORE-Element.

CDWA Lite (2006)	6.1 Indexing Measurements Set	Text (controlled values, controlled format)	Yes	Not mandatory	5.1 Display Measurements is "Highly recommended".
Spectrum 5.1	Dimension (and sub-elements)	Text (controlled vocabulary, controlled values, controlled format)	Yes	Not specified	The obligation level is determined by the institution.
digiCULT	Maße [eng.: Measurements]	Text (controlled vocabulary)	Yes	Recommended	
museum-digital	Dimensions	Text (controlled vocabulary)	Yes	Recommended	The dimensions can also be entered in museum-digital in a string or in a differentiated manner.

ID Datenfeld

mds0008

Event in object history [element set] (mandatory)

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- [Obligation level](#)
- [Recording notes](#)
- [Expression in LIDO v. 1.0](#)
- [Expression in LIDO v. 1.1](#)
- [Comparison with relevant standards and database models](#)

Definition

Element set for describing an event in the history of the object

Repeatable

Yes, the element set is repeatable.

Obligation level

Mandatory

Recording notes

Events in object history can provide information about the production, creation, discovery, etc. of an object. An event provides information about what happened (event type), who was involved (person/entity), where (place) and when (date) it took place. Each event must have at least one "who", "where" or "when". At least one event in the history of the object must be described. If no such information is available for an object, at least one period of time during which the item was created or entered the collection should be given to form an event. Any number of events can be given for each object.

 CARE: Knowledge gaps in the object's history should always be disclosed (e.g. by stating "not documented" or "not known to us" in the data elements "[Person/corporate body](#)", "[Date](#)", "[Place](#)"). Uncertainties or attributions that originate, for example, from the surviving collection entry documentation should be contextualized in a separate data element "Event description" (in LIDO: `<lido:eventDescriptionSet>/<descriptiveNoteValue>`).

Expression in LIDO v. 1.0

```

<lido:eventWrap>
  <lido:eventSet>
    <lido:event>
      <lido:eventType>
        <lido:conceptID lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00099"
>http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00007</lido:conceptID>
        <lido:term xml:lang="de">Herstellung</lido:term>
        <lido:term xml:lang="en">Production</lido:term>
      </lido:eventType>
      <lido:eventActor>
        <lido:actorInRole>
          <lido:actor>
            <lido:actorID lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org
/lido00099">https://d-nb.info/gnd/24495-8</lido:actorID>
            <lido:nameActorSet>
              <lido:appellationValue xml:lang="de">Nixdorf Computer
AG</lido:appellationValue>
              <lido:appellationValue xml:lang="en">Nixdorf Computer AG<
/lido:appellationValue>
            </lido:nameActorSet>
          </lido:actor>
        </lido:actorInRole>
      </lido:eventActor>
      <lido:eventDate>
        <lido:date>
          <lido:earliestDate>1983</lido:earliestDate>
          <lido:latestDate>1983</lido:latestDate>
        </lido:date>
      </lido:eventDate>
      <lido:eventPlace>
        <lido:place>
          <lido:placeID lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00099"
>https://sws.geonames.org/2855745/</lido:placeID>
          <lido:namePlaceSet>
            <lido:appellationValue xml:lang="de">Paderborn</lido:
appellationValue>
            <lido:appellationValue xml:lang="en">Paderborn</lido:
appellationValue>
          </lido:namePlaceSet>
        </lido:place>
      </lido:eventPlace>
    </lido:event>
  </lido:eventSet>
</lido:eventWrap>

```

Expression in LIDO v. 1.1

```

<lido:eventWrap>
  <lido:eventSet>
    <lido:event>
      <lido:eventType>
        <skos:Concept rdf:about="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00007">
          <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="de">Herstellung</skos:prefLabel>
          <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="en">Production</skos:prefLabel>
        </skos:Concept>
      </lido:eventType>
      <lido:eventActor>
        <lido:actorInRole>
          <lido:actor>
            <lido:actorID lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00099">https://d-nb.info/gnd/24495-8</lido:actorID>
            <lido:nameActorSet>
              <lido:appellationValue xml:lang="de">Nixdorf Computer AG</lido:appellationValue>
              <lido:appellationValue xml:lang="en">Nixdorf Computer AG</lido:appellationValue>
            </lido:nameActorSet>
          </lido:actor>
        </lido:actorInRole>
      </lido:eventActor>
      <lido:eventDate>
        <lido:date>
          <lido:earliestDate>1983</lido:earliestDate>
          <lido:latestDate>1983</lido:latestDate>
        </lido:date>
      </lido:eventDate>
      <lido:eventPlace>
        <lido:place>
          <lido:placeID lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00099">https://sws.geonames.org/2855745/</lido:placeID>
          <lido:namePlaceSet>
            <lido:appellationValue xml:lang="de">Paderborn</lido:appellationValue>
            <lido:appellationValue xml:lang="en">Paderborn</lido:appellationValue>
          </lido:namePlaceSet>
        </lido:place>
      </lido:eventPlace>
    </lido:event>
  </lido:eventSet>
</lido:eventWrap>

```

Comparison with relevant standards and database models

Standard	Element name	Text /URI	Repeatable	Obligation level	Comment
German Digital Library: Requirements for data provided	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	
German Digital Library LIDO application profile (DDB-LIDO)	<eventWrap>	Not applicable	Yes (<eventSet>)	Conditionally mandatory Recommended	Mandatory if sub-elements exist.
CCC-LIDO Application profile	<eventWrap>	Not applicable	Yes (<eventSet>)	Conditionally mandatory Recommended	
DFG Basic Data Record	(No match, see comment)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Recommended (see comment)	The German Research Foundation recommends documenting a central "relevant" event by specifying a location, naming "relevant" persons (with details of their role) and specifying a "time of origin".

DFG Practical Guidelines on Digitisation: LIDO core metadata	Event lido:eventSet /lido:event	Not applicable	Yes	Mandatory if available	
Europeana Data Model (EDM)	<edm:Event>	Not applicable	Yes	Not mandatory	Europeana not (yet) uses <edm:Event>. This report recommends the introduction of <edm:Event>.
EODEM application profile	Object Production Group /lido: eventWrap /lido:eventSet /lido:event	Not applicable	No	Mandatory	EODEM includes a production event (Object Production Group).
Categories for the Description of Works of Art (2024)	4 Creation 17.1 Historical /Cultural Events 23 Ownership /Collecting History	Not applicable	No/No specification	Recommended	CORE-Element: Creation
CDWA Lite (2006)	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	The creation of the object is documented in the following elements: 3rd Display Creator (mandatory) and 4th Indexing Creator Wrapper (mandatory), 12th Display Creation Date (mandatory) and 13th Indexing Dates Wrapper (mandatory).
Spectrum 5.1	Object production information Acquisition information Object collection information Common Procedural Units	Text	Yes	Not specified	The obligation level is determined by the institution.
digiCULT	Ereignis [eng.: Event]	Not applicable	Yes	Recommended	
museum-digital	Event	Not applicable	No	Recommended	

Event type (mandatory)

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Definition

Type of event in the history of the object

Other possible database element names

Type of event

Text/URI

Text and/or URI

Repeatable

No, only one Event type per event

Obligation level

Mandatory

Recording notes

For specifying the event type, the use of the event type vocabulary from the [LIDO terminology](#) is recommended. A German and an English preferred term as well as a persistent URI are provided for each event type.

 CARE: If nothing more is known about the provenance and date of an object beyond its access to the collection, an appropriate event type should be selected. Gaps in knowledge of the object's history should always be disclosed (e. g. by entering "not documented" or "not known to us" in the "person /entity", "date", "place" data elements). Uncertainties or attributions, e.g. from the surviving collection entry documentation, should be contextualised in a separate data element "Event description" (in LIDO: `<lido:eventDescriptionSet>/<descriptiveNoteValue>`).

Terminology recommendations

[LIDO terminology](#) (for eventType)

Examples

URI	Preferred term
http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00007	Production
http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00002	Finding (Activity)
http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido01151	Change of physical control or legal title

http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00006	Modification (Activity)
http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00033	Excavation
http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00011	Use

Expression in LIDO v1.0

```
<lido:eventWrap>
  <lido:eventSet>
    <lido:event>
      <lido:eventType>
        <lido:conceptID lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00099"
>http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00007</lido:conceptID>
        <lido:term xml:lang="de">Herstellung</lido:term>
          <lido:term xml:lang="en">Production</lido:term>
        </lido:eventType>
      </lido:event>
    </lido:eventSet>
  </lido:eventWrap>
```

Expression in LIDO v1.1

```
<lido:eventWrap>
  <lido:eventSet>
    <lido:event>
      <lido:eventType>
        <skos:Concept rdf:about="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00007">
          <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="de">Herstellung</skos:prefLabel>
          <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="en">Production</skos:prefLabel>
        </skos:Concept>
      </lido:eventType>
    </lido:event>
  </lido:eventSet>
</lido:eventWrap>
```

Comparison with relevant standards and database models

Standard	Element name	Text/URI	Repeatable	Obligation level	Comment
German Digital Library: Metadata requirements for data provision	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	
German Digital Library LIDO application profile (DDB-LIDO)	<eventType> / <conceptID>	Text (controlled vocabulary) and URI	No	Conditionally mandatory Recommended	Mandatory if <eventWrap> exists. The event type cannot be repeated within an event. Any number of events can be assigned to an object.
CCC-LIDO Application profile	<eventType> / <conceptID>	Text (controlled vocabulary) and URI	No	Conditionally mandatory Recommended	
DFG Basic Data Record	(No match, see comment)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Recommended	The German Research Foundation recommends documenting a central "relevant" event by specifying a location, naming a "relevant" person (with details of their role) and specifying a "time of origin". Depending on the context, this is "production", "find" or "collecting".
DFG Practical Guidelines on Digitisation: LIDO core metadata	Event lido:eventSet/lido:event/lido:eventType	Text (controlled vocabulary) and URI	No	Mandatory if available	

Europeana Data Model (EDM)	../edm:Event/edm:hasType	Text and/or URI	Yes	Not mandatory	Europeana not (yet) uses <edm:Event>. This report recommends the introduction of <edm:Event>.
EODEM application profile	Object Production Group /lido:eventType/lido:conceptID /lido:eventType/lido:term	Text (controlled vocabulary) and/or URI	No	Mandatory	EODEM includes a production event (Object Production Group).
Categories for the Description of Works of Art (2024)	4 Creation 17.1.1 Event Type 23 Ownership /Collecting History	Text (controlled vocabulary)	No	Recommended/Not mandatory	CORE element: Creation Event Type: Vocabulary recommendation: Art & Architecture Thesaurus , in particular the hierarchies Events < http://vocab.getty.edu/hier/aat/300054722 > and Associated Concepts < http://vocab.getty.edu/hier/aat/300055126 >
CDWA Lite (2006)	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	
Spectrum 5.1	(No match for a number of relevant events, see comment) Procedure title	Text	Yes	Not specified	The event type can be derived from the element sets Object production information , Acquisition information , Object collection information and other Spectrum procedures. The obligation level is determined by the institution.
digiCULT	(Data element name is determined by the event type)	Text (controlled vocabulary) and URI	No	Recommended	
museum-digital	(Data element name is determined by the event type)	Text (controlled vocabulary) and URI	No	Recommended	Museum-digital database provides its own vocabulary for event types: https://event-types.museum-digital.org/ .

ID data element

mds0009

Person/corporate body (conditionally mandatory)

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Definition

In the history of the object, the person or corporate body involved in the event described

Other possible database element names

Artist

Producer

Organisation

Name of the person involved

Name of the institution

Owner

Text/URI

Text and/or URI

Repeatable

Yes

Obligation level

At least one event in the history of the object is mandatory.

In addition to the Event type, each event must have at least one "who", "where" or "when".

Recording notes

It is recommended to specify names of persons/corporate bodies both in a text element and separately using URIs from authority files. There are various recommendations for specifying preferred names, depending on the application. An important reference is the [Integrated Authority File](#) (GND).

In the case of data delivery to the [German Digital Library](#), the delivery of URIs from the [Integrated Authority File](#) is strongly recommended for the identification of persons and corporate bodies.

It is recommended that the role played by the person/corporate body mentioned in the described event in the object history is specified in a separate element. If this is not possible, the role specification should be added to the name in such a way that it can be extracted rule-based during export, e.g. "Last name, first name (role: [role name])".

If the person/corporate body that produced the object cannot be identified, a separate data element (in LIDO: [<lido:culture>](#)) should be used to specify the geographical, stylistic or cultural attribution of the object, if possible.

 CARE: Knowledge gaps in the object's history should always be disclosed (e.g. by stating “not documented” or “not known to us” in the data elements “Person/entity”, “Date”, “Location”). Uncertainties or attributions that originate, for example, from the surviving collection entry documentation should be contextualized in a separate data element “Event description” (in LIDO: `<lido:eventDescriptionSet></descriptiveNoteValue>`). If the persons/corporate bodies involved can be researched and identified retrospectively, but do not have a unique identifier in the [Integrated Authority File](#), collaborative knowledge databases such as [Wikidata](#) are suitable for generating unique identifiers.

Terminology recommendation

[Integrated Authority File](#) (GND, German National Library): The following search interfaces provide a convenient way to search the GND: <https://explore.gnd.network/> (GND-Explorer), <https://lobid.org/gnd> (lobid-gnd), <https://swb.bsz-bw.de/DB=2.104/> (OGND). German Digital Library: Preferred name in [Entity Facts](#) is decisive.

[Union List of Artist Names](#) (for persons and corporate bodies active in various functions in the arts)

[Virtual International Authority File](#)

[Wikidata](#)

Examples

URI	Preferred name
https://d-nb.info/gnd/1048652033	Hinghaus, Walter
http://vocab.getty.edu/ulan/500593279	Zippel, Eva
http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q5594	Antonello da Messina
https://d-nb.info/gnd/118521713	Commodus, Römischer Reich, Kaiser [eng.: Commodus, Emperor of Rome, 161-192]
https://d-nb.info/gnd/119904489X	Kotys II., Bosphorisches Reich, König [eng.: Cotys II, Bosphoran Kingdom]
https://d-nb.info/gnd/2120183-3	Gilbert & George
http://vocab.getty.edu/ulan/500524769	Royal Porcelain Manufactory, Berlin
https://d-nb.info/gnd/83740-4	Artaria & Fontaine à Mannheim (Firma) [engl.: Artaria & Fontaine, Bookseller in Mannheim]
https://d-nb.info/gnd/24495-8	Nixdorf Computer AG

Expression in LIDO (v1.0 and v1.1)

```
<lido:eventWrap>
  <lido:eventSet>
    <lido:event>
      <lido:eventActor>
        <lido:actorInRole>
          <lido:actor>
            <lido:actorID lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00099">https://d-
nb.info/gnd/24495-8</lido:actorID>
            <lido:nameActorSet>
              <lido:appellationValue xml:lang="de">Nixdorf Computer AG</lido:
appellationValue>
              <lido:appellationValue xml:lang="en">Nixdorf
Computer AG</lido:appellationValue>
            </lido:nameActorSet>
          </lido:actor>
        </lido:actorInRole>
      </lido:eventActor>
    </lido:event>
  </lido:eventSet>
</lido:eventWrap>
```

Comparison with relevant standards and database models

Standard	Element name	Text/URI	Repeatable	Obligation level	Comment
----------	--------------	----------	------------	------------------	---------

German Digital Library: Metadata requirements for data provision	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	
German Digital Library LIDO application profile (DDB-LIDO)	<eventActor>	Text (controlled vocabulary) and/or URI	Yes	Conditionally mandatory	Mandatory if sub-elements exist. GND IDs are the basis for creating or linking to entity pages, for instance on persons or corporate bodies, in the portal.
CCC-LIDO Application profile	who <eventActor>	Text (controlled vocabulary) and/or URI (GND)	Yes	Conditionally mandatory	In the CCC-Lido application profile, only values from controlled vocabularies (GND) are transferred to the 'Person/organisation' search filter.
DFG Basic Data Record	Source Object Relevant Person	Text (controlled vocabulary) and/or URI	Yes	Recommended	
DFG Practical Guidelines on Digitisation: LIDO core metadata	Identifiable actors involved in the event <eventSet> / <event> / <eventActor>	Text (controlled vocabulary) and/or URI	Yes	Mandatory if available	The DFG Practical Guidelines on Digitisation recommend that additional information on the cultural context in the LIDO-Element <culture> is provided, especially if no specific producer or user of the object can be named.
Europeana Data Model (EDM)	<dc:creator> <dc:contributor> <dc:publisher> <edm:agent>	Text (controlled vocabulary) and/or URI	Yes	Recommended	
EODEM application profile	Maker Identifier, Maker Sort Name /lido:eventActor/lido:actorInRole /lido:actor/lido:actorID /lido:eventActor/lido:actorInRole /lido:actor/ lido:nameActorSet/lido:appellationValue	Text (controlled vocabulary) and/or URI	Yes	Not mandatory	
Categories for the Description of Works of Art (2024)	Production: 4.1. Creator Description and sub-elements Commissioning: 4.5 Commissioner Excavation: 17.3.3 Excavator Other events: 17.1.5. Event Agent	Text (controlled vocabulary)	Yes	Recommended	CORE elements: 4.1.3 Creator Identity and 4.1.4 Creator Role Vocabulary recommendation: Union List of Artist Names and other standardised files on persons and corporate bodies.
CDWA Lite (2006)	4.1.1.1 Name of Creator	Text (controlled vocabulary)	Yes	Mandatory	If several creators are specified, 4.1.1 Name Creator Set is repeated. Vocabulary recommendation: Union List of Artist Names and other standard files on persons and corporate bodies.
Spectrum 5.1	Organisation information Person information Procedure manager People information	Text (controlled vocabulary)	Yes	Not specified	There are specified elements for information on persons and organisations in the element sets Object production information , Acquisition information , Object collection information and other Spectrum procedures. The obligation level is determined by the institution.
digiCULT	Künstler/Hersteller/Vorbesitzer etc. (actorInRole) [engl.: Artist /Producer/Previous owner etc. (actorInRole)]	Text (controlled vocabulary) and/or URI	Yes	Recommended	
museum-digital	Who?	Text (controlled vocabulary) and URI	Yes	Recommended	

ID data element

mds0010

Date (conditionally mandatory)

Contents

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Definition

Date (precise date or time period) when the event in the object history occurred

Other possible database element names

Date / Period

Times

Date of production

Date of origin

Text/URI

Text (Date format; [ISO 8601](#) requested)

Repeatable

No

Obligation level

At least one event in the history of the object is mandatory.

In addition to the Event type, each event must have at least one "who", "where" or "when".

Recording notes

Date entries are made in standardized format (preferably [ISO 8601](#)).

Time spans are specified in two separate data elements. The first data element contains the earliest possible or known date and the second data element contains the latest possible or known date on which the event in the history of the object occurred.

Date information can also be entered in free text form (for uncertain information, periods/epochs, etc.). This is recorded in a separate data field (in LIDO: `<lido:displayDate>` for verbal information or `<lido:periodName>` for periods/epochs respectively).

 CARE: Knowledge gaps in the object's history should always be disclosed (e.g. by stating "not documented" or "not known to us" in the data elements "Person/entity", "Date", "Location"). Uncertainties or attributions that originate from the surviving documentation of the collection entry, for example, should be contextualized in a separate data element "Event description" (in LIDO: `<lido:eventDescriptionSet>/<descriptiveNoteValue>`).

Format recommendation

[ISO 8601](#)

[Extended Date/Time Format \(EDTF\)](#)

Examples

1801/1900

1969-07-21/1969-08-15

-377/-299

1983/1987

1983

1596/1605

Expression in LIDO (v1.0 and v1.1)

```
<lido:eventWrap>
  <lido:eventSet>
    <lido:event>
      <lido:eventDate>
        <lido:date>
          <lido:earliestDate>1983</lido:earliestDate>
          <lido:latestDate>1983</lido:latestDate>
        </lido:date>
      </lido:eventDate>
    </lido:event>
  </lido:eventSet>
</lido:eventWrap>
```

Comparison with relevant standards and database models

Standard	Element name	Text /URI	Repeatable	Obligation level	Comment
German Digital Library: Metadata requirements for data provision	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	
German Digital Library LIDO application profile (DDB-LIDO)	<eventDate>	Text	No	Conditionally mandatory	Mandatory if sub-elements exist.
CCC-LIDO Application profile	when <eventDate>	Text	No	Conditionally mandatory	
DFG Basic Data Record	Source Object Time of Origin	Text	Not specified	Recommended	
DFG Practical Guidelines on Digitisation: LIDO core metadata	Time period of event <eventDate>	Text	No	Mandatory, if available	The DFG Practical Guidelines on Digitisation require additional date information in text form where such information is available, in which any inaccuracies can be expressed. The LIDO element <eventDate> /<displayDate> is used for this purpose. An indication of the period of the event in the LIDO element <periodName> is recommended.
Europeana Data Model (EDM)	<dc:date> <dcterms:created> <dcterms:issued> <edm:TimeSpan>	Text and/or URI	Ja	Not mandatory	
EODEM application profile	Earliest Production Date und Latest Production Date /lido:eventDate/lido:date/lido:earliestDate und /lido:latestDate	Text	No	Not mandatory	Corresponds largely to the elements 12. Element: Display Creation Date and 13.1.2 Sub-element: Earliest Date as well as 13.1.3 Sub-element: Latest Date in CDWA Lite for the dating of the object's production.

Categories for the Description of Works of Art (2024)	Production: 4.2.1 Earliest Date and 4.2.2 Latest Date Commissioning: 4.5.2.1 Earliest Date and 4.5.2.2 Latest Date Excavation: 17.3.4.1 Earliest Date and 17.3.4.2 Latest Date Other events: 17.1.3.1 Earliest Date and 17.1.3.2 Latest Date	Text (Date format)	No	Recommended/Not mandatory	CORE elements: 4.2 Creation Date , 4.2.1 Earliest Date and 4.2.2 Latest Date for the production of the object
CDWA Lite (2006)	13.1.2 Earliest Date and 13.1.3 Latest Date	Text (Date format)	No	Mandatory	13.1. Indexing date sets is repeatable.
Spectrum 5.1	Procedure begin date Procedure end date Date information	Text (Date format)	Yes	Not specified	There are specified elements for information on dates in the element sets Object production information , Acquisition information , Object collection information and other Spectrum procedures. The obligation level is determined by the institution.
digiCULT	Datierung (eventDate) [engl.: Date (eventDate)]	Text	No	Recommended	
museum-digital	When?	Text	No	Recommended	

ID data element

mds0011

Place (conditionally mandatory)

Contents

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Definition

Place where the event described in the object history occurred

Other possible database element names

Geographic reference

Place of discovery

Mint

Text/URI

Text and/or URI

Repeatable

Yes

Obligation level

At least one event in the history of the object is mandatory.

In addition to the Event type, each event must have at least one "who", "where" or "when".

Recording notes

It is recommended to specify names of persons/entities both in a text element and separately using URIs from authority files. If both current and historical place names are recorded, these should be documented in separate data elements or otherwise identified.

 CARE: Knowledge gaps in the object's history should always be disclosed (e.g. by stating "not documented" or "not known to us" in the data elements "Person/entity", "Date", "Location"). Uncertainties or attributions that originate, for example, from the surviving collection entry documentation should be contextualized in a separate data element "Event description" (in LIDO: `<lido:eventDescriptionSet>/<descriptiveNoteValue>`). References to the location of collection items from colonial contexts often originate from historical records or documents. As the names and political affiliations of places have changed, it is often not possible to reconstruct which place it is today. In this case, the assignment of URIs from standard vocabularies should not imply any supposed accuracy. Instead, the historical name (in its literal form) should be published via a text data field (in LIDO: `<lido:namePlaceSet>/<lido:appellationValue>`). Under certain circumstances, places of origin should not be published at all, e. g. to protect artefacts from looting or plants from illegal collection.

Terminology recommendation

[Geonames](#)

[Thesaurus of Geographic Names \(TGN\)](#)

[Wikidata](#)

Integrated Authority File (GND, German National Library): The following search interfaces provide a convenient way to search the GND: <https://explore.gnd.network/> (GND-Explorer), <https://lobid.org/gnd> (lobid-gnd), <https://swb.bsz-bw.de/DB=2.104/> (OGND)

Pleiades (for historical place names)

Examples

URI	Preferred name
http://vocab.getty.edu/tgn/7006464	Prague
https://sws.geonames.org/2928376/	Eutritzsch
https://d-nb.info/gnd/4005728-8	Berlin
https://sws.geonames.org/2855745/	Paderborn
https://d-nb.info/gnd/4007955-7	Brandenburg
http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q142	France
https://pleiades.stoa.org/places/668331	Palmyra
http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q20135	Grand Duchy of Hesse
https://d-nb.info/gnd/2015221-8	Karl-Marx-Stadt
https://sws.geonames.org/3208037/	Kloster Eberbach [eng.: Eberbach Abbey]
https://pleiades.stoa.org/places/216788	Deultum

Expression in LIDO (v1.0 und v1.1)

```
<lido:eventWrap>
  <lido:eventSet>
    <lido:event>
      <lido:eventPlace>
        <lido:place>
          <lido:placeID lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00099">https://sws.
geonames.org/2855745/</lido:placeID>
          <lido:namePlaceSet>
            <lido:appellationValue xml:lang="de">Paderborn</lido:appellationValue>
            <lido:appellationValue xml:lang="en">Paderborn</lido:
appellationValue>
          </lido:namePlaceSet>
        </lido:place>
      </lido:eventPlace>
    </lido:event>
  </lido:eventSet>
</lido:eventWrap>
```

Comparison with relevant standards and database models

Standard	Element name	Text/URI	Repeatable	Obligation level	Comment
German Digital Library: Metadata requirements for data provision	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	
German Digital Library LIDO application profile (DDB-LIDO)	<eventPlace>	Text and/or URI	Yes	Conditionally mandatory if sub-elements exist.	
CCC-LIDO Application profile	where <eventPlace>	Text and/or URI	Yes	Conditionally mandatory	In the CCC-Lido application profile, only values from controlled vocabularies (Wikidata, GeoNames, TGN, GND) are transferred to the 'Location' search filter.

DFG Basic Data Record		Text and/or URI	Not specified	Recommended	
DFG Practical Guidelines on Digitisation: LIDO core metadata	Place where event took place <eventPlace>	Text and/or URI	Yes	Mandatory, if available	The DFG Practical Guidelines on Digitisation also recommend georeferencing using <place> / <gml>.
Europeana Data Model (EDM)	<edm:Place> / <skos:prefLabel>	Text	No	Not mandatory	
EODEM application profile	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not mandatory	
Categories for the Description of Works of Art (2024)	Production: 4.3. Creation Place Commissioning: 4.5.3 Commission Place Excavation: 17.3.1 Discovery /Excavation Place Other events: 17.1.4 Event Place	Text (controlled vocabulary)	Yes	Not mandatory	Vocabulary recommendation: Thesaurus of Geographic Names and other geographic standard data
CDWA Lite (2006)	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	
Spectrum 5.1	Place information	Text (controlled vocabulary) and URI	Yes	Not specified	There are specified elements for information on places in the element sets Object production information , Object collection information and other Spectrum procedures. The obligation level is determined by the institution.
digiCULT	Herstellungsort/Fundort /Gebrauchsort etc. (eventPlace) [eng.: Place of production/discovery /use]	Text (controlled vocabulary) and URI	Yes	Recommended	
museum-digital	Where?	Text (controlled vocabulary) and URI	Yes	Recommended	

ID data element

mds0012

Subject keyword (recommended)

Contents

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Definition

Designation of an item depicted on the object/work or of a subject covered by the object or work

Other possible database element names

Keyword

Iconography

Themes

Motifs

Content/representation

Reference (who, what, where)

Text/URI

Text (controlled vocabulary) and URI

Repeatable

Yes

Obligation level

Recommended

Recording notes

A term used to describe an item depicted on an object/work or a subject covered. The purpose of keywords is to make objects easier to find in online searches. Several subject keywords can be assigned to an object. The data element should be repeatable and only one subject keyword should be assigned per element.

Keywords intended to place the object in a larger systematic or classificatory context should be recorded in the "[Classification](#)" data element. Terms given in the "[Object type or designation](#)" element should not be repeated in the "Subject keyword" element.

In addition to subjects and themes (in LIDO: [<lido:subjectConcept>](#)), individually identifiable persons or places depicted in an object or work may also be recorded as subject keywords. This should be done in separate fields so that they can be transferred to the LIDO elements [<lido:subjectActor>](#) and [<lido:subjectPlace>](#) during data export.

 CARE: Persons from the communities of origin should be involved in the cataloguing work to allow for different interpretation models and possible interpretations. Alternative vocabularies are helpful to mitigate the Eurocentric perspective (see Terminology recommendation).

Terminology recommendation

Art & Architecture Thesaurus

Integrated Authority File (GND, German National Library). The following search interfaces provide a convenient way to search the GND: <https://explore.gnd.network/> (GND-Explorer), <https://lobid.org/gnd> (lobid-gnd), <https://swb.bsz-bw.de/DB=2.104/> (OGND)

[Wikidata](#)

[Iconclass](#)

[Iconography Authority](#)

 [CARE: Chinese Iconography Thesaurus \(CIT\)](#) for cataloguing of China's visual culture

Examples

Relating to an item depicted in the object/work, or its subject matter

URI	Preferred term
http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300008626	landscapes (environments)
https://d-nb.info/gnd/4006054-8	Bestattung [eng: Burial <LCSH match>]
http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q26886	combine harvester
http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300379749	phoenixes
https://d-nb.info/gnd/4165633-7	Kreuz Christi [eng: Holy Cross <LCSH match>]
https://iconclass.org/73D312	Christ's prayer in the Garden of Gethsemane during the night
http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q1821239	Day of Judgment
https://iconclass.org/44B162	coronation of a ruler
https://d-nb.info/gnd/4324124-4	Vanitas
https://d-nb.info/gnd/124113788	Rotkäppchen, Literarische Gestalt [eng.: Little Red Riding Hood]

Expression in LIDO v1.0

```
<lido:objectRelationWrap>
  <lido:subjectWrap>
    <lido:subjectSet>
      <lido:subject lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00525">
        <lido:subjectConcept>
          <lido:conceptID lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00099">http://vocab.
getty.edu/aat/300008626</lido:conceptID>
          <lido:term xml:lang="de">Landschaft (Lebensraum)</lido:term>
          <lido:term xml:lang="en">landscapes (environments)</lido:term>
        </lido:subjectConcept>
      </lido:subject>
    </lido:subjectSet>
  </lido:subjectWrap>
</lido:objectRelationWrap>
```

Expression in LIDO v1.1

```

<lido:objectRelationWrap>
  <lido:subjectWrap>
    <lido:subjectSet>
      <lido:subject lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00525">
        <lido:subjectConcept>
          <skos:Concept rdf:about="http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300008626">
            <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="de">Landschaft (Lebensraum)</skos:
prefLabel>
            <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="en">landscapes (environments)</skos:
prefLabel>
          </skos:Concept>
        </lido:subjectConcept>
      </lido:subject>
    </lido:subjectSet>
  </lido:subjectWrap>
</lido:objectRelationWrap>

```

Comparison with relevant standards and database models

Standard	Element name	Text URI	Repeatable	Obligation level	Comment
German Digital Library: Metadata requirements for data provision	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	
German Digital Library LIDO application profile (DDB-LIDO)	<subjectConcept>	Text (controlled vocabulary) and URI	Yes	Conditionally mandatory	Mandatory if sub-elements exist.
CCC-LIDO Application profile	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	
DFG Basic Data Record	Source Object Type of Content	Text and/or URI	Not specified	Recommended	In the DFG Basic Data Record , "Source Object Type of Content" is only recommended in the 'digital-mix' category. This only partly corresponds to the "Subject keyword" data element.
DFG Practical Guidelines on Digitisation: LIDO core metadata	Theme / Content <subjectSet>	Text and/or URI	Yes	Mandatory if available	In the DFG Practical Guidelines on Digitisation , the indexing of general terms in the LIDO element <subjectConcept> or of individual terms for persons/corporate bodies in <subjectActor>, places in <subjectPlace>, events in <subjectEvent>, objects in <subjectObject> or dates in <subjectDate> is mandatory if the information is available.
Europeana Data Model (EDM)	dc:subject	Text (controlled vocabulary) and/or URI	Yes	Conditionally mandatory	In the Europeana Data Model <dc:subject> (subject keyword/classification) OR <dc:type> (object type) OR <dcterms:spatial> (keyword [place/location depicted/represented]) OR <dcterms:temporal>(keyword [time depicted/as subject]) are mandatory.
EODEM application profile	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not mandatory	
Categories for the Description of Works of Art (2024)	16.2. General Subject Terms 16.3. Specific Subject Terms	Text (controlled vocabulary)	Yes	Recommended	CORE-Element: 16.2. General Subject Terms Vocabulary recommendation: Art & Architecture Thesaurus , Iconclass or general terms in another controlled vocabulary or standard vocabularies for persons, places, etc.

CDWA Lite (2006)	15.1.2 Indexing Subject Term	Text (controlled vocabulary)	Yes	Recommended	Vocabulary recommendation: Art & Architecture Thesaurus , Iconclass or general terms in another controlled vocabulary or standard vocabularies for persons, places, etc.
Spectrum 5.1	Content - concept Content - activity Content - person Content - place Content - object	Text (controlled vocabulary)	Yes	Not specified	More elements for differentiated content indexing are available under Object description information . The obligation level is determined by the institution.
digiCULT	Darstellung [eng.: Representation] Ikonographie [eng.: Iconography]	Text (controlled vocabulary) and/or URI	Yes	Recommended	The data element "Representation" in digiCULT is a kind of element set consisting of iconography, depicted place, depicted person, depicted date and annotation.
museum-digital	Keyword or relation	Text (controlled vocabulary) and/or URI	Yes	Recommended	museum-digital recommends that keywords should be used in singular, lemmatised form; no diminutives or word formations on '-like' or '-shaped' should be used, and keywords should not be concatenated or embedded in hierarchical structures. See: https://de.handbook.museum-digital.info . In PUQI, a data quality measurement procedure and manual for improving data quality in museum-digital, three to nine keywords are recommended. Museum-digital does not make a distinction between "keyword" and "subject category", contrary to the Minimum Record Recommendation.

ID data element

mds0013

Media file [element set] (mandatory)

Data elements (cataloguing)

- [Link to media file \(mandatory\)](#)
- [Usage rights of media file \(mandatory\)](#)
- [Rights holder of media file \(conditionally mandatory\)](#)
- [Alternative text \(recommended\)](#)

Data elements (export)

- [Media file: type of media file \(mandatory\)](#)

Link to media file (mandatory)

Contents

- [Definition](#)
- [Other possible database element names](#)
- [Text/URI](#)
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- [Comparison with relevant standards and database models](#)
- [ID data element](#)

Definition

Digital representation (e.g. digital image, video, 3D object, audio file) of the cultural heritage object, which is accessed via a direct stable link

Other possible database element names

Link to the digital object

ID digital copy

Medium

Image

Text/URI

URI

Repeatable

Yes

Obligation level

Mandatory

Recording notes

The media file should be made available via a persistent URL. If a link cannot be provided, an alternative delivery method for the media file should be agreed with portals or other data recipients.

If different images, videos, etc. are available, several media files may be provided. In this case, the file with the best available quality should be selected. If necessary, additional media files for subtitles, audio description and transcription can be provided for reasons of digital accessibility of audio and video files.

 CARE: Sensitive items, such as religious or ritual artefacts, that are not appropriate for viewing or should be reserved for a specific group of people, may not be published with an image. A placeholder image may be used instead (see expressions in LIDO). Institutions should consult with people from the communities of origin. Ideally, ethical considerations should be documented in the database.

Examples

https://fotothek.slub-dresden.de/fotos/df/pos-2019-a/0000000/df_pos-2019-a_0000108.jpg

<http://skd-online-collection.skd.museum/imagescreate/image?id=1218449&type=gross>

https://brandenburg.museum-digital.de/data/brandenburg/images/63/67099-ex_002_213/wolkensituation_6b_919_m/wolkensituation-6b-919-m-67099.jpg

http://www.tierstimmenarchiv.de/recordings/Pavo_cristatus_Kr0063_01_short.mp3 (Audio)

<https://st.museum-digital.de/singleimage?resourcenr=1954&noiif=1> (3D)

Expression in LIDO (v1.0 and v1.1)

```
<lido:resourceWrap>
  <lido:resourceSet lido:sortorder="1">
    <lido:resourceRepresentation lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00464">
      <lido:linkResource lido:formatResource="image/png">https://www.bruecke-museum.de/ds-images/61779_front.png</lido:linkResource>
    </lido:resourceRepresentation>
  </lido:resourceSet>
</lido:resourceWrap>
```

💡 CARE:

Example from the portal "Collections in Colonial Contexts":

```
<lido:resourceWrap>
  <lido:resourceSet lido:sortorder="1">
    <lido:resourceRepresentation lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00467">
      <lido:linkResource lido:formatResource="text/html">https://ccc.deutsche-digitale-bibliothek.de/</lido:linkResource>
    </lido:resourceRepresentation>
  </lido:resourceSet>
</lido:resourceWrap>
```

Comparison with relevant standards and database models

Standard	Element name	Text /URI	Repeatable	Obligation level	Comment
German Digital Library: Metadata requirements for data provision	VorschauBild [eng.: Preview image] Link zum digitalen Objekt: Mediendatei [eng.: Digital object link: media file]	URI	Yes	Conditionally mandatory (see Comment)	Either a link to the media file or to the object in the media viewer or to the object in context is mandatory. A preview image is also mandatory for audio and video files and 3D objects.
German Digital Library LIDO application profile (DDB-LIDO)	<resourceSet / <resourceRepresentation / <linkResource>	URI	Yes	Conditionally mandatory (see Comment)	Mandatory if <recordInfoLink> is not available. A preview image is also mandatory for audio and video files and 3D objects.
CCC-LIDO Application profile	<resourceSet / <resourceRepresentation / <linkResource>	URI	Yes	Conditionally mandatory (see Comment)	
DFG Basic Data Record	Digital copy identifier (ID)	URI	Not specified	Mandatory	The "Digital Copy Identifier (ID)" should resolve as a LOD URI for the digitised item.
DFG Practical Guidelines on Digitisation: LIDO core metadata	Representations: <resourceSet / <resourceRepresentation / <linkResource>	URI	Yes	Mandatory if available	
Europeana Data Model (EDM)	<edm:isShownBy>	URI	Yes	Conditionally mandatory	In the Europeana Data Model (EDM) EITHER <edm:isShownBy> OR <edm:isShownAt> must be available.
EODEM application profile	Image /lido:resourceWrap /lido:resourceSet/ lido:resourceRepresentation/lido:linkResource	Text or URI	No	Mandatory	
Categories for the Description of Works of Art (2024)	(No equivalent)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	A persistent URL is not provided for in the Categories for the Description of Works of Art . Instead, the media file can be identified in various elements of group 26.2 Image Label/Identification https://www.getty.edu/publications/categories-description-works-art/categories/object-architecture-group/26/#s26-2 .

CDWA Lite (2006)	22.1.1 Link Resource	Text	No	Not mandatory	
Spectrum 5.1	Reproduction number	Text	No	Not specified	The obligation level is determined by the institution.
digiCULT	Medium	URI	Yes	Recommended	
museum-digital	Image, PDF, Video, Audio, 3D-object	URI	Yes	Mandatory	

ID data element

mds0014

Usage rights of media file (mandatory)

Contents

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- [Other possible database element names](#)
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Definition

Indication of copyright status and usage rights of the digital representation

Other possible database element names

Legal status of media file

Terms of use media file

Licence

Rights information media file

Legal status of the image

Rights table

Text/URI

URI + optionally text (controlled vocabulary)

Repeatable

No, only one rights statement per media file

Obligation level

Mandatory

Recording notes

This data element specifies a valid rights notice or licence for the media file. This indicates the extent to which the media file may be used.

If you are planning to deliver data to the [German Digital Library](#), you have to select a licence or rights statement from [Rechteangaben in der Deutschen Digitalen Bibliothek](#) [eng.: Rights statements in the German Digital Library].

The rights to the cultural heritage object (e.g. a painting) are included in the media file that digitally represents the object. If the cultural heritage object is (still) protected by copyright, the author and the holder of the rights of use of the cultural heritage object must always be stated. This is done in a separate data element (in LIDO: `<lido:rightsWorkSet>` / `<lido:rightsHolder>`). If the cultural heritage object is in the public domain and is not a three-dimensional object (for such objects, reproduction may involve a threshold of originality), no new rights will normally arise in the digital representation or media file.

Further information can be found in the publication [In Bewegung. Die Rechtsfibel für Digitalisierungsprojekte in Kulturerbe-Einrichtungen](#) [eng.: In motion. The legal primer for digitisation projects in cultural heritage institutions]. In addition, the [NFD14Culture Legal Helpdesk](#) can be contacted with legal questions relating to the publication of digitised cultural material. The [legal department](#) of the German Digital Library is available to answer [legal questions](#) related to the delivery of data to the German Digital Library.

 CARE: In the case of collection items from colonial contexts, the primary cultural sovereignty lies with the communities of origin. The „[Traditional Knowledge \(TK\) Labels](#)“ or „[Biocultural \(BC\) Labels](#)“ supplement [Creative Commons Licenses](#) and provide information about procedural arrangements for accessing this material and/or about uses that have been deemed generally acceptable. Labels are applied by cultural and knowledge institutions in partnership with communities (see expression in LIDO).

Lists

[Rechteangaben in der Deutschen Digitalen Bibliothek](#) [eng.: Rights statements in the German Digital Library]

Rights statements of rightsstatements.org

[Creative Commons licenses list](#)

Examples

URI	Vorzugsbezeichnung
https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/mark/1.0/	Public Domain Mark 1.0 Universal
https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/	CC0 1.0 Universal
http://rightsstatements.org/vocab/InC/1.0/	In Copyright

Expression in LIDO v1.0

```
<lido:resourceWrap>
  <lido:resourceSet>
    <lido:rightsResource>
      <lido:rightsType>
        <lido:conceptID lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00099"
>https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/mark/1.0/</lido:conceptID>
        <lido:term xml:lang="de">Public Domain Mark 1.0 Universell</lido:term>
        <lido:term xml:lang="en">Public Domain Mark 1.0 Universal</lido:term>
      </lido:rightsType>
    </lido:rightsResource>
  </lido:resourceSet>
</lido:resourceWrap>
```

 CARE:

```
<lido:resourceWrap>
  <lido:resourceSet>
    <lido:rightsResource>
      <lido:rightsType>
        <lido:conceptID lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00099"
lido:source="Local Contexts">https://localcontexts.org/label/tk-multiple-communities/</lido:conceptID>
        <lido:term>TK Multiple Communities (TK MC)</lido:term>
      </lido:rightsType>
      <lido:creditLine xml:lang="en">
        Responsibility and ownership over this material is spread across several distinct communities.
        Use will be dependent upon discussion and negotiation with the multiple communities named herein [name N.N. and
        community name N.N.]. Decisions about use will need to be decided collectively. As an external user of this
        material you are asked to recognize and respect cultural protocols in relation to the use of this material and
        clear your intended use with the relevant communities.
      </lido:creditLine>
    </lido:rightsResource>
  </lido:resourceSet>
</lido:resourceWrap>
```

Expression in LIDO v1.1

```

<lido:resourceWrap>
  <lido:resourceSet>
    <lido:rightsResource>
      <lido:rightsType>
        <skos:Concept rdf:about="https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/mark
/1.0/">
          <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="de">Public Domain Mark 1.0 Universell</skos:prefLabel>
          <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="en">Public Domain Mark 1.0 Universal</skos:prefLabel>
        </skos:Concept>
      </lido:rightsType>
    </lido:rightsResource>
  </lido:resourceSet>
</lido:resourceWrap>

```

Comparison with relevant standards and database models

Standard	Element name	Text/URI	Repeatable	Obligation level	Comment
German Digital Library: Metadata requirements for data provision	Rechtsstatus für das Digitale Objekt [Rights status of digital object]	URI	No	Mandatory	A licence or rights statement must be selected from the Rechteangaben in der Deutschen Digitalen Bibliothek .
German Digital Library LIDO application profile (DDB-LIDO)	<rightsResource> / <rightsType>/ <conceptID>	URI	No	Mandatory	
CCC-LIDO Application profile	<rightsResource> / <rightsType>/ <conceptID>	URI	No	Mandatory	
DFG Basic Data Record	Digital Copy Terms of Use	URI	Not specified	Mandatory	
DFG Practical Guidelines on Digitisation: LIDO core metadata	<resourceSet> / <rightsResource>	Text (controlled vocabulary) and /or URI	Yes	Mandatory if available	
Europeana Data Model (EDM)	<edm:rights>	URI	No	Mandatory	It is mandatory for the element <edm:rights> to contain a value from https://pro.europeana.eu/page/available-rights-statements .
EODEM application profile	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	
Categories for the Description of Works of Art (2024)	26.2.12 Image Copyright /Restrictions	Text	Not specified	Not mandatory	Rights to the cultural heritage object: 22.1 Copyright Statement
CDWA Lite (2006)	22.1.5 Rights for Resource	Text	Yes	Not mandatory	Rights to the cultural heritage object: 20th Rights for Work
Spectrum 5.1	Right reference number Right type	Text (controlled vocabulary)	Yes	Not specified	The obligation level is determined by the institution.
digiCULT	Lizenztyp [eng.: License type]	Text (controlled vocabulary) and URI	No	Recommended	
museum-digital	Rechtsstatus der Abbildung [eng.: Rights status of image]	URI	No	Mandatory	

ID data element

mds0015

Rights holder of media file (conditionally mandatory)

Contents

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- [ID data element](#)

Definition

Holder of usage rights of the digital representation

Other possible database element names

Rights holder of media file

Rights holder of the digital copy

Rights holder of the image

Text/URI

Text and/or URI

Repeatable

Yes

Obligation level

Mandatory if the media file is not in the public domain

Recording notes

This data element is used to specify the author or holder of the usage rights of the media file. If both of these are available, they must be entered in separate elements. This data element is mandatory for media files that are not in the public domain. If the media file is in the public domain, the author may be named, but not the rights holder. If necessary, e. g. the photographer or those involved in digitization may also be provided in a separate data element (in LIDO: [<lido:resourceSource>](#)). If the author or photographer is not known, this can be indicated (e.g., by stating "not documented").

 CARE: In the case of collection items from colonial contexts, the primary cultural sovereignty lies with the communities of origin. Please note the information on the [Usage rights of the media file](#) (see LIDO expression).

Terminology recommendations and lists

[International Standard Identifier for Libraries and Related Organisations \(ISIL\)](#)

[Integrated Authority File](#) (GND, German National Library). The following search interfaces provide a convenient way to search the GND: <https://explore.gnd.network/> (GND-Explorer), <https://lobid.org/gnd> (lobid-gnd), <https://swb.bsz-bw.de/DB=2.104/> (OGND)

[Wikidata](#)

Examples

URI	Preferred name
https://ld.zdb-services.de/resource/organisations/DE-MUS-016119	Berlinische Galerie - Landesmuseum für Moderne Kunst, Fotografie und Architektur
https://ld.zdb-services.de/resource/organisations/DE-MUS-859718	Deutsches Stuhlbaumuseum Rabenau / Sachsen e.V.
https://ld.zdb-services.de/resource/organisations/DE-2888	Stiftung Kraftwerk Hirschfelde
https://d-nb.info/gnd/136281699	Schmidt-Glassner, Helga
https://d-nb.info/gnd/1088445-2	Verwertungsgesellschaft Bild-Kunst

Expression in LIDO (v1.0 and v1.1)

```
<lido:resourceWrap>
  <lido:resourceSet>
    <lido:resourceSource lido:type="photographer">
      <lido:legalBodyName>
        <lido:appellationValue xml:lang="de">Jürges, Detlef</lido:appellationValue>
      </lido:legalBodyName>
    </lido:resourceSource>
    <lido:rightsResource>
      <lido:rightsHolder>
        <lido:legalBodyID lido:source="isil" lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org
/lido00099">https://ld.zdb-services.de/resource/organisations/DE-MUS-163819</lido:legalBodyID>
        <lido:legalBodyName>
          <lido:appellationValue xml:lang="de">Museum August Kestner</lido:
appellationValue>
          <lido:appellationValue xml:lang="en">Museum August Kestner</lido:
appellationValue>
        </lido:legalBodyName>
      </lido:rightsHolder>
    </lido:rightsResource>
  </lido:resourceSet>
</lido:resourceWrap>
```

CARE:

```
<lido:resourceWrap>
  <lido:resourceSet>
    <lido:resourceSource lido:type="photographer">
      <lido:legalBodyName>
        <lido:appellationValue xml:lang="de">Haase, Matthias</lido:appellationValue>
      </lido:legalBodyName>
    </lido:resourceSource>
    <lido:rightsResource>
      <lido:rightsHolder>
        <lido:legalBodyID lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00099" lido:source="
Local Contexts">https://localcontexts.org/label/tk-multiple-communities/</lido:legalBodyID>
        <lido:legalBodyName>
          <lido:appellationValue xml:lang="en">Arapaso, Bará, Barasana, Desana, Karapanã,
Kotiria, Kubeo, Makuna, Mirity-tapuya, Pira-tapuya, Siriano, Tariana, Tukano, Tuyuca, Tatuyo, Taiwano, Yuruti
(the last three live only in Colombia)</lido:appellationValue>
        </lido:legalBodyName>
      </lido:rightsHolder>
    </lido:rightsResource>
  </lido:resourceSet>
</lido:resourceWrap>
```

Comparison with relevant standards and database models

Standard	Element name	Text/URI	Repeatable	Obligation level	Comment
----------	--------------	----------	------------	------------------	---------

German Digital Library: Metadata requirements for data provision	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	
German Digital Library LIDO application profile (DDB-LIDO)	<rightsResource> / <rightsHolder> / <legalBodyName> / <appellationValue>	Text	Yes	Conditionally mandatory (see comment)	Mandatory if media file is not in the public domain
CCC-LIDO Application profile	<rightsResource> / <rightsHolder> / <legalBodyName> / <appellationValue>	Text	Yes	Conditionally mandatory (see comment)	
DFG Basic Data Record	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not mandatory	
DFG Practical Guidelines on Digitisation: LIDO core metadata	Representations: <rightsSet> / <rightsResource> / <rightsHolder>	Text and/or URI	Yes	Mandatory if available	
Europeana Data Model (EDM)	<dc:rights>	Text	Yes	Not mandatory	
EODEM application profile	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not mandatory	
Categories for the Description of Works of Art (2024)	26.2.12.1. Image Copyright Holder	Text (controlled vocabulary)	Not specified	Not mandatory	Vocabulary recommendation: Union List of Artist Names and other standard vocabularies for persons and entities Management of rights in the cultural heritage object: 22.2 Copyright Holder Name
CDWA Lite (2006)	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	
Spectrum 5.1	Right holder	Text (controlled vocabulary)	Yes	Not specified	The obligation level is determined by the institution.
digiCULT	Rechteinhaber [eng.: Rights holder]	Text (controlled vocabulary) and /or URI	Yes	Recommended	
museum-digital	Rechteinhaber der Abbildung [eng.: Rights holder of image]	Text and/or URI	Yes	Mandatory	

ID data element

mds0016

Alternative text (recommended)

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Definition

The alternative text is a description of the image content to make the media file (digital representation) accessible to people who cannot see it.

Other possible database element names

Alt-Text

Alternative text

Text/URI

Text

Repeatable

Yes

Obligation level

Recommended

Recording notes

Alternative text is particularly important for people with visual impairments who use screen readers or other assistive technologies. Alternative text should concisely and vividly describe the visible elements, style and medium that are central to understanding. Care should be taken to highlight important details that contribute to the meaning or atmosphere of the object/work depicted. The language should be simple, clear and as objective as possible.

For more information on how to write an alternative text, see: [German Federation of the Blind and Partially Sighted \(DBSV\)](#)

Examples

Painting (Impressionism): "This oil painting by Claude Monet shows an early morning scene with soft pink and blue colours, depicting a row of dimly lit houses along a river. The quick brushstrokes and the reflection of light on the water convey a calm, misty atmosphere."

Sculpture (modern art): "Abstract bronze sculpture by Henry Moore, approximately two metres high. The sculpture shows intertwined forms that appear both organic and fluid, reminiscent of human figures leaning against each other."

Photograph (portrait): "Black and white photograph of an elderly man looking directly into the camera. The man has deep wrinkles and a serious expression. The light falls on his face from the side, emphasising the texture of his skin and the intensity of his gaze."

Historical artefact (medieval tapestry): "The detailed medieval tapestry shows a battle scene with numerous knights on horseback. The knights carry colourful coats of arms and lances. Tents and flags can be seen in the background, suggesting a bustling camp life."

Expression in LIDO (v1.0 and v1.1)

```
<lido:resourceWrap>
  <lido:resourceSet>
    <lido:resourceDescription lido:type="https://www.wikidata.org/entity/P11265" xml:lang="de">Das
Ölgemälde von Claude Monet zeigt eine frühmorgendliche Szene mit sanften rosa und blauen Farbtönen, die eine
Reihe schwach beleuchteter Häuser entlang eines Flusses darstellt. Die schnellen Pinselstriche und die
Lichtreflexion auf dem Wasser vermitteln eine ruhige, neblige Atmosphäre.</lido:resourceDescription>
    <lido:resourceDescription lido:type="https://www.wikidata.org/entity/P11265" xml:lang="en">This oil
painting by Claude Monet shows an early morning scene with soft pink and blue colours, depicting a row of dimly
lit houses along a river. The quick brushstrokes and the reflection of light on the water convey a calm, misty
atmosphere.</lido:resourceDescription>
  </lido:resourceSet>
</lido:resourceWrap>
```

Comparison with relevant standards and database models

Alternative texts are not addressed in the standards and database models analysed.

ID data element

mds0017

Data elements (export)

Data fields that are usually populated during or after export from the local database system:

- Record ID (mandatory)
- Record language (mandatory)
- Record type (mandatory)
- Repository of object (mandatory)
- Institution providing record (mandatory)
- Media file: type of media file (mandatory)
- Usage rights of metadata record (mandatory)
- Link to published metadata record (recommended)
- Record date (recommended)

Record ID (mandatory)

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Definition

Globally unique identifier for the data record on the object

Other possible database element names

Metadata record identifier

Internal ID

Data record ID

Text/URI

Text or URI

Repeatable

No

Obligation level

Mandatory

Notes

For compatibility with the LIDO harvesting format, the unique identifier for the record must appear in two places: First, the local identifier for the record is requested (`<lido:recordID>`). This is automatically generated in the database.

Second, a unique identifier for the record is required, which is valid across institutions (`<lido:lidoRecID>`). A combination of the [ISIL](#) and local record number should be used to ensure uniqueness beyond the institution.

Examples

DE-MUS-452619/49291

DE-Y2_08000066_bh601503

DE-MUS-813712_ZMB_Mam_002165

<https://hdl.handle.net/21.11107/2a42a7c0-075c-41b4-b838-6b12f7a06685>

Expression in LIDO (v1.0 and v1.1)

```
<lido:lidoRecID lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00100">DE-MUS-016317/61779</lido:lidoRecID>
```

```

<lido:recordWrap>
  <lido:recordID lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00100">61779</lido:recordID>
</lido:recordWrap>

```

Comparison with relevant standards and database models

Standard	Element name	Text/URI	Repeatable	Obligation level	Comment
German Digital Library: Metadata requirements for data provision	Identifikator für den Datensatz	Text	No	Mandatory	
German Digital Library LIDO application profile (DDB-LIDO)	<lidoReclD> <recordID>	Text	No	Mandatory	
CCC-LIDO Application profile	<lidoReclD> <recordID>	Text	No	Mandatory	
DFG Basic Data Record	Metadata Record Identifier (ID)	URI	Not specified	Mandatory	The identifier is required in the form of a LOD URI. Example: https://hdl.handle.net/21.11107/2a42a7c0-075c-41b4-b838-6b12f7a06685
DFG Practical Guidelines on Digitisation: LIDO core metadata	Identifiers for LIDO dataset and object <lidoReclD> and <recordID>	Text	Yes	Mandatory	
Europeana Data Model (EDM)	<ore:Aggregation> / @rdf:about <edm:aggregatedCHO>	Text or URI	No	Mandatory	Either a LOD URI or an internal identifier is expected.
EODEM application profile	LIDO Record ID <lidoReclD> und <recordID>	Text	No	Mandatory	
Categories for the Description of Works of Art (2024)	25.7. Object/Work Record ID	Text (kontrolliertes Format)	No	Not mandatory	
CDWA Lite (2006)	21.1 Record ID	Text	Yes	Mandatory	
Spectrum 5.1	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	
digiCULT	ID Datensatz [eng.: ID of record]	Text	No	Mandatory	
museum-digital	record-ID	Text	No	Mandatory	

ID data element

mds0018

Record language (mandatory)

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Definition

Indication of the language of the metadata record

Other possible database element names

Language labelling

Language attributes

Language of the entry

Internal language abbreviation

Text/URI

Text (controlled format; two-letter [ISO-639-1](#) language codes preferred)

Repeatable

No

Obligation level

Mandatory

Notes

This data element indicates the language in which the record is available. It is required for compatibility of the Minimum Record Recommendation with the LIDO harvesting format.

If certain free-text structured information, such as the [Object title or name](#) or an [Object description](#), is also available in other languages, this is indicated separately for the corresponding individual data elements. The language labelling of individual data elements will usually have priority over the general language labelling of the data record in the processing of individual elements in portals.

In addition to the language of the dataset and the language labelling of individual data field values, the language of the cultural heritage object can be specified. This is mandatory when delivering data to Europeana for cultural heritage objects with the media type "Text", and it is implemented in the LIDO element `<lido:classification>` with the type attribute='language' for data deliveries to Europeana via the [German Digital Library](#). In Europeana EDM, the language of the cultural heritage object is indicated in the EDM element `<dc:language>`.

In LIDO, the language is not indicated by an element, but by the `xml:lang` attribute. Two-character language codes should be used for language labelling, if available for the language in question. Alternatively, three-character language codes may be used. This follows the recommendations of [W3](#) and [Europeana](#).

Lists

[ISO-639-1](#) (two-letter language codes) preferred. As an alternative, [ISO 639-2](#) / [ISO 639-3](#) (three-letter language codes) can also be used.

Examples

de
en
fr
fa
nr
mas

Expression in LIDO (v1.0 and v1.1)

```
<lido:descriptiveMetadata xml:lang="de">
<lido:administrativeMetadata xml:lang="de">
```

```
<lido:objectIdentificationWrap>
  <lido:titleWrap>
    <lido:titleSet>
      <lido:appellationValue xml:lang="de">Bildnis der Schwester Agathe</lido:
appellationValue>
      <lido:appellationValue xml:lang="en">Portrait of the Artist's Sister
Agathe</lido:appellationValue>
      <lido:appellationValue xml:lang="fr">Portrait de sa soeur</lido:
appellationValue>
    </lido:titleSet>
  </lido:titleWrap>
</lido:objectIdentificationWrap>
```

Comparison with relevant standards and database models

Standard	Element name	Text /URI	Repeatable	Obligation level	Comment
German Digital Library: Metadata requirements for data provision	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	
German Digital Library LIDO application profile (DDB-LIDO)	<descriptiveMetadata xml:lang> and <administrativeMetadata xml:lang>	Not applicable : attribute	No	Mandatory	Language labelling is mandatory in LIDO at record level. Therefore, it is also mandatory in the DDB-LIDO application profile.
DFG Basic Data Record	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	
DFG Practical Guidelines on Digitisation: LIDO core metadata	<descriptiveMetadata xml:lang> and <administrativeMetadata xml:lang>	Not applicable : attribute	No	Mandatory (see comment)	Language labelling is mandatory in LIDO at record level. Therefore, it is also mandatory in the LIDO core metadata of the DFG Practical Guidelines on Digitisation .
Europeana Data Model (EDM)	<edm:language>	Text (controlled vocabulary)	No	Mandatory (see comment)	The element is completed by the Europeana Data Ingestion Team at the time of import, based on the language of the data partner. In EDM, it is also strongly recommended to indicate the language of each element. Like LIDO, EDM provides the language attribute xml:lang using the ISO-639-2 standard for this purpose. In EDM it is also mandatory to label the language of the cultural heritage object for text objects (letters, postcards, brochures, etc.). This is done in the <dc:language> element.
EODEM application profile	Record Language /lido:descriptiveMetadata /@xml:lang /lido:administrativeMetadata /@xml:lang	Text (controlled vocabulary)	No	Mandatory	

Spectrum 5.1	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Spectrum provides the following object-related language information: Object name/title language , Content – language , Inscription language , Text language .
digiCULT	/ido:descriptiveMetadata /@xml:lang /ido:administrativeMetadata /@xml:lang	Not applicable : attribute	No	Mandatory	
museum-digital	Language	Text (controlled vocabulary)	No	Mandatory	The language for content and navigation is selected automatically, but can also be controlled using language selectors.

ID data element

mds0019

Record type (mandatory)

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- [ID data element](#)

Definition

Type of data record regarding whether it describes a single object or a group of objects

Other possible database element names

Data record type

Single object/object group

Text/URI

Text (controlled vocabulary) and URI

Repeatable

No

Obligation level

Mandatory

Notes

This data element indicates whether the record is for a single object or a group of objects. It is required to ensure compatibility of the Minimum Record Recommendation with the LIDO harvesting format. For single objects, the element value should be <http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00141> (= Item-level record).

Examples

URI	Preferred term
http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00141	Item-level record
http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00453	Group-level record

Expression in LIDO v1.0

```

<lido:recordWrap>
  <lido:recordID lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00100">00039758</lido:recordID>
  <lido:recordType>
    <lido:conceptID lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00099">http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00141</lido:conceptID>
    <lido:term xml:lang="de">Einzelobjekt (Katalogisierungsebene)</lido:term>
    <lido:term xml:lang="en">Item-level record</lido:term>
  </lido:recordType>
</lido:recordWrap>

```

Expression in LIDO v1.1

```

<lido:recordWrap>
  <lido:recordID lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00100">00039758</lido:recordID>
  <lido:recordType>
    <skos:Concept rdf:about="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00141">
      <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="de">Einzelobjekt (Katalogisierungsebene)</skos:prefLabel>
      <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="en">Item-level record</skos:prefLabel>
    </skos:Concept>
  </lido:recordType>
</lido:recordWrap>

```

Comparison with relevant standards and database models

Standard	Element name	Text/URI	Repeatable	Obligation level	Comment
German Digital Library: Metadata requirements for data provision	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	
German Digital Library LIDO application profile (DDB-LIDO)	<recordType> / <conceptID>	URI	No	Mandatory	
CCC-LIDO Application profile	<recordType> / <conceptID>	URI	No	Mandatory	
DFG Basic Data Record	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	The DFG Basic Data Record assumes that only "individual objects" are recorded. The record type is therefore not listed as a separate data element.
DFG Practical Guidelines on Digitisation: LIDO core metadata	Dataset: <recordType>	Text (controlled vocabulary) and URI	No	Mandatory	
Europeana Data Model (EDM)	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	
EODEM application profile	LIDO Record Type Identifier und LIDO Record Type Keyword /lido:recordWrap/lido:recordType/lido:conceptID und /lido:term	Text (controlled vocabulary) and URI	No	Mandatory	
Categories for the Description of Works of Art (2024)	1.1. Catalog Level	Text (controlled vocabulary)	Not specified	Recommended	CORE element
CDWA Lite (2006)	21.2 Record Type	Text (controlled vocabulary)	No	Mandatory	
Spectrum 5.1	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	The Number of objects (numerical value) can be used to generate information about the record type. The obligation level of the Number of objects is determined by the institution.
digiCULT		Text (controlled vocabulary) and URI	No	Mandatory	

museum-digital	single object / object group	Text and URI	No	Mandatory	
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ID data element

mds0020

Repository of object (mandatory)

Contents

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Definition

Name of the institution holding the cultural heritage object

Other possible database element names

Institution

Museum

Collection

Museum location

Name of the museum

Assigned museum

Text/URI

Text (controlled vocabulary) and URI

Repeatable

Yes

Obligation level

Mandatory

Notes

A unique identifier for the institution is required. The preferred identifier is the [International Standard Identifier for Libraries and Related Organisations \(ISIL\)](#). This data element refers to the institution holding the object. In addition, a free text entry of the institution name is helpful for display in portals.

Terminology recommendations and lists

[International Standard Identifier for Libraries and Related Organisations \(ISIL\)](#)

[Integrated Authority File](#) (GND, German National Library): The following search interfaces provide a convenient way to search the GND: <https://explore.gnd.network/> (GND-Explorer), <https://lobid.org/gnd> (lobid-gnd), <https://swb.bsz-bw.de/DB=2.104/> (OGND)

[Wikidata](#)

Examples

URI	Preferred name
https://ld.zdb-services.de/resource/organisations/DE-MUS-016119	Berlinische Galerie - Landesmuseum für Moderne Kunst, Fotografie und Architektur
https://ld.zdb-services.de/resource/organisations/DE-MUS-859718	Deutsches Stuhlbaumuseum Rabenau / Sachsen e.V.
https://ld.zdb-services.de/resource/organisations/DE-MUS-403018	Industriemuseum Elmshorn
https://d-nb.info/gnd/2134213-1	Hochschule der Künste Berlin. Archiv
https://d-nb.info/gnd/1043476709	Kulturstiftung des Hauses Hessen

Expression in LIDO (v1.0 and v1.1)

```
<lido:repositoryWrap>
  <lido:repositorySet lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00475">
    <lido:repositoryName>
      <lido:legalBodyID lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00099">https://ld.
zdb-services.de/resource/organisations/DE-MUS-048017</lido:legalBodyID>
      <lido:legalBodyName>
        <lido:appellationValue xml:lang="de">Städel Museum</lido:appellationValue>
          <lido:appellationValue xml:lang="en">Städel Museum</lido:appellationValue>
        </lido:legalBodyName>
      </lido:repositoryName>
    </lido:repositorySet>
  </lido:repositoryWrap>
```

Comparison with relevant standards and database models

Standard	Element name	Text/URI	Repeatable	Obligation level	Comment
German Digital Library: Metadata requirements for data provision	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	
German Digital Library LIDO application profile (DDB-LIDO)	<repositorySet> / <repositoryName> / <legalBodyName>	Text	No	Conditionally mandatory	Mandatory if <namePlaceSet> is available
CCC-LIDO Application profile	Current location <repositorySet> / <repositoryName> / <legalBodyName>	Text	No	Conditionally mandatory	Mandatory if a <namePlaceSet> is available. If the value is missing in the data, the name of the location is added via the registration. The value appears in the 'Current location' search filter.
DFG Basic Data Record	Source Object Institution	Text and/or URI	Not specified	Mandatory	In addition to our recommendation, the DFG Basic Data Record recommends to indicate the collection to which the object is assigned.
DFG Practical Guidelines on Digitisation: LIDO core metadata	Repository/location: <repositorySet> / <repositoryName> / <legalBodyName>	Text	No	Mandatory if available	
Europeana Data Model (EDM)	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	
EODEM application profile	Lender Identifier and Lender Name (repository) /lido:repositoryWrap/lido:repositorySet/ lido:repositoryName/lido:legalBodyID und /lido:legalBodyName/lido:appellationValue	Text and URI	No	Mandatory	
Categories for the Description of Works of Art (2024)	21.2. Repository/Geographic Location	Text (controlled vocabulary)	Not specified	Recommended	CORE-Element
CDWA Lite (2006)	14.1.1 Location/Repository Name	Text (controlled vocabulary)	No	Mandatory	If several facilities are specified, 14.1 Location /Repository Set is repeated.

Spectrum 5.1	Organisation's main body (if applicable also Organisation's sub-body) with Organisation's reference number	Text (controlled vocabulary) and URI	No	Not specified	The obligation level is determined by the institution.
digiCULT	Museum	Text (controlled vocabulary) and URI	No	Mandatory	In digiCULT , the ISIL is used to automatically assign the custodian institution.
museum-digital	Name of museum (with address, coordinates and ideally ISIL)	Text (controlled vocabulary) and URI	No	Mandatory	If the holding institution is not the same as the institution that created the record, in museum-digital the 'Whereabouts' tab can also be used to indicate the location of the object.

ID data element

mds0021

Institution providing record (mandatory)

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Definition

Name of the institution that created the record

Other possible database element names

Providing organisation

Data partner

Institution metadata record

Name of the museum

Text/URI

Text (controlled vocabulary) and URI

Repeatable

Yes

Obligation level

Mandatory

Notes

A unique identifier for the institution is required. The preferred identifier is the [International Standard Identifier for Libraries and Related Organisations \(ISIL\)](#). This data element refers to the institution that has created the record. In addition, a free text entry of the institution name is helpful for display in portals.

Terminology recommendations and lists

[International Standard Identifier for Libraries and Related Organisations \(ISIL\)](#)

[Integrated Authority File \(GND, German National Library\)](#): The following search interfaces provide a convenient way to search the GND: <https://explore.gnd.network/> (GND-Explorer), <https://lobid.org/gnd> (lobid-gnd), <https://swb.bsz-bw.de/DB=2.104/> (OGND)

[Wikidata](#)

Examples

URI	Preferred name
https://ld.zdb-services.de/resource/organisations/DE-MUS-016119	Berlinische Galerie - Landesmuseum für Moderne Kunst, Fotografie und Architektur

https://ld.zdb-services.de/resource/organisations/DE-MUS-859718	Deutsches Stuhlbaumuseum Rabenau / Sachsen e.V.
https://ld.zdb-services.de/resource/organisations/DE-MUS-403018	Industriemuseum Elmshorn
https://d-nb.info/gnd/2134213-1	Hochschule der Künste Berlin. Archiv
https://d-nb.info/gnd/1043476709	Kulturstiftung des Hauses Hessen

Expression in LIDO (v1.0 and v1.1)

```

<lido:recordWrap>
  <lido:recordSource>
    <lido:legalBodyID lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00099">https://ld.zdb-services.de
/resource/organisations/DE-MUS-275818</lido:legalBodyID>
    <lido:legalBodyName>
      <lido:appellationValue xml:lang="de">Freilichtmuseum Roscheider Hof</lido:appellationValue>
      <lido:appellationValue xml:lang="en">Roscheider Hof Open Air Museum</lido:
appellationValue>
    </lido:legalBodyName>
  </lido:recordSource>
  <lido:recordSource lido:type="dataProvider">
    <lido:legalBodyID lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00099">https://www.wikidata.org/wiki
/Q1360745</lido:legalBodyID>
    <lido:legalBodyName>
      <lido:appellationValue xml:lang="de">museum-digital</lido:appellationValue>
      <lido:appellationValue xml:lang="en">museum-digital</lido:appellationValue>
    </lido:legalBodyName>
  </lido:recordSource>
</lido:recordWrap>

```

Comparison with relevant standards and database models

Standard	Element name	Text/URI	Repeatable	Obligation level	Comment
German Digital Library: Metadata requirements for data provision	Identifikator für den Datenpartner [eng.: ID of data provider]	Text and URI	Not specified	Mandatory	
German Digital Library LIDO application profile (DDB-LIDO)	<recordSource> / <legalBodyID>	URI	No	Mandatory	
CCC-LIDO Application profile	<recordSource> / <legalBodyID>	URI	No	Mandatory	
DFG Basic Data Record	Metadata Record Institution	Text and/or URI	Not specified	Mandatory	
DFG Practical Guidelines on Digitisation: LIDO core metadata	Dataset: <recordSource>	Text	Yes	Mandatory	
Europeana Data Model (EDM)	<edm:dataProvider>	Text and/or URI	No	Mandatory	
EODEM application profile	Lender Identifier und Lender Name (record source) /lido:recordWrap/ lido:recordSource/lido:legalBodyID und /lido: legalBodyName/lido:appellationValue	Text and URI	Yes	Mandatory	
Categories for the Description of Works of Art (2024)	25.1. Cataloging Institution	Text (controlled vocabulary)	Not specified	Not mandatory	
CDWA Lite (2006)	21.3 Record Source	Text (controlled vocabulary)	Yes	Not mandatory	
Spectrum 5.1	Organisation's main body (if applicable also Organisation's sub-body) with Organisation's reference number	Text (controlled vocabulary) and URI	No	Not specified	The obligation level is determined by the institution.
digiCULT	Museum	Text (controlled vocabulary) and URI	Yes	Mandatory	In digiCULT, the ISIL is used to automatically assign the institution that provides the record.

museum-digital	Name of museum (with address, coordinates and ideally ISIL)]	Text (controlled vocabulary) and URI	Yes	Mandatory	The museum information is created by regional admins.
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ID data element

mds0022

Media file: type of media file (mandatory)

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Definition

Type of media file

Other possible database element names

Type of reproduction

Media type

Text/URI

Text (controlled vocabulary) and/or URI

Repeatable

No

Obligation level

Mandatory

(DDB: additionally, the media format is mandatory)

Notes

For technical reasons, it is mandatory to specify the media type (in LIDO: `<lido:resourceType></lido:term>`) when publishing to portals such as [German Digital Library](#) and [Europeana](#). Only one media type can be specified per media file.

The [media format](#) (MIME type) should additionally be specified in a separate data element (in LIDO: `Attribut lido:formatResource` of the element `<lido:linkResource>`).

Terminology recommendations

DDB media type: <http://ddb.vocnet.org/medientyp>

Europeana Media Formats: <https://pro.europeana.eu/page/media-formats-mime-types>

[Art & Architecture Thesaurus](#)

Examples

URI (DDB)	Preferred term
-----------	----------------

http://ddb.vocnet.org/medientyp/mt001	Audio
http://ddb.vocnet.org/medientyp/mt002	Image
http://ddb.vocnet.org/medientyp/mt003	Text
http://ddb.vocnet.org/medientyp/mt005	Video
http://ddb.vocnet.org/medientyp/mt010	3D

Expression in LIDO v1.0

```
<lido:resourceWrap>
  <lido:resourceSet>
    <lido:resourceRepresentation lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00464">
      <lido:linkResource lido:formatResource="image/jpeg">http://diglib.hab.de/varia/haumzeichnungen/zl-i-03676-08/max/000001.jpg</lido:linkResource>
    </lido:resourceRepresentation>
    <lido:resourceType>
      <lido:term xml:lang="de">Bild</lido:term>
      <lido:term xml:lang="en">image</lido:term>
    </lido:resourceType>
  </lido:resourceSet>
</lido:resourceWrap>
```

Expression in LIDO v1.1

```
<lido:resourceWrap>
  <lido:resourceSet>
    <lido:resourceRepresentation lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00464">
      <lido:linkResource lido:formatResource="image/jpeg">http://diglib.hab.de/varia/haumzeichnungen/zl-i-03676-08/max/000001.jpg</lido:linkResource>
    </lido:resourceRepresentation>
    <lido:resourceType>
      <skos:Concept rdf:about="http://ddb.vocnet.org/medientyp/mt002">
        <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="de">Bild</skos:prefLabel>
        <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="en">image</skos:prefLabel>
      </skos:Concept>
    </lido:resourceType>
  </lido:resourceSet>
</lido:resourceWrap>
```

Comparison with relevant standards and database models

Standard	Element name	Text /URI	Repeatable	Obligation level	Comment
German Digital Library: Metadata requirements for data provision	Medientyp [eng.: media type]	Text	No	Mandatory (also IANA media type mandatory)	In contrast to the minimum data set recommendation, in the German Digital Library the Medientyp [eng.: media type] does not refer to the digital representation, but to the cultural heritage object. For example, if the cultural heritage object is a postcard, the media type for a data delivery to the German Digital Library must be "Text", regardless of whether the media file is a PDF or a JPG.
German Digital Library LIDO application profile (DDB-LIDO)	<resourceSet> / <resourceType> > / <term>	Text	No	Mandatory (also IANA media type mandatory)	In addition, the IANA media type (MIME type) must be specified for data deliveries to the German Digital Library. This should be provided via the attribute value of formatResource.
CCC-LIDO Application profile	<resourceSet> / <resourceType> > / <term> and /or <conceptID>	Text and /or URI	No	Mandatory (also IANA media type mandatory)	

DFG Basic Data Record	Digital Copy Media Type and Format	Text (controlled vocabulary) and /or URI	Not specified	Mandatory	Media type and format are combined in the DFG Basic Data Record ; a specification according to https://www.iana.org/assignments/media-types/media-types.xhtml is preferred.
DFG Practical Guidelines on Digitisation: LIDO core metadata	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not specified	
Europeana Data Model (EDM)	<edm:type>	Text (controlled vocabulary)	No	Mandatory	
EODEM application profile	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not specified	
Categories for the Description of Works of Art (2024)	26.2.2. Image Type	Text (controlled vocabulary)	Yes	Not mandatory	Vocabulary recommendation: Art & Architecture Thesaurus or general terms in another controlled vocabulary
CDWA Lite (2006)	22.1.4. Resource Type	Text (controlled vocabulary)	Yes	Not mandatory	Vocabulary recommendation: Art & Architecture Thesaurus
Spectrum 5.1	Reproduction type Reproduction format	Text (controlled vocabulary)	No	Not specified	Repeatability: Only one statement per reproduction. The obligation level is determined by the institution.
digiCULT	MIME Type	Text	No	Mandatory	The media type in digiCULT is derived from the format specification (MIME type).
museum-digital	(No match)	Text	No	Mandatory	The media type is selected in museum-digital when a resource is uploaded: If an image is uploaded, this corresponds to the media type "image"; if a video is uploaded, this corresponds to the media type "video".

ID data element

mds0023

Usage rights of metadata record (mandatory)

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Definition

Indication of copyright status and usage rights of the metadata record

Other possible database element names

Legal status metadata

Terms of use metadata set

Metadata licence

Text/URI

URI + optionally text (controlled vocabulary)

Repeatable

No

Obligation level

Mandatory

Notes

This data element specifies a valid rights notice or licence for the metadata record. This indicates the extent to which the object information may be used. If you are planning to deliver data to the German Digital Library, you must select a licence or rights statement from [Rechteangaben in der Deutschen Digitalen Bibliothek](#) [eng.: Rights statements in the German Digital Library].

If the object description text is subject to intellectual property rights, the corresponding legal status should be indicated in a separate data field (in LIDO: `<lid o:objectDescriptionRights>`, from LIDO v.1.1) (see also [Object description](#)).

Lists

[Rechteangaben in der Deutschen Digitalen Bibliothek](#) [eng.: Rights statements in the German Digital Library]

[Rightsstatements.org](#)

[Creative Commons Licenses](#)

Examples

URI	Preferred term
-----	----------------

https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/	CC0 1.0 Universal
https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/4.0/	CC BY-NC-SA 4.0 - Attribution-Noncommercial-Sharealike 4.0 International

Expression in LIDO v1.0

```
<lido:recordRights>
  <lido:rightsType>
    <lido:conceptID lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00099">https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/</lido:conceptID>
    <lido:term xml:lang="de">CC0 1.0 Universell</lido:term>
    <lido:term xml:lang="en">CC0 1.0 Universal</lido:term>
  </lido:rightsType>
</lido:recordRights>
```

Expression in LIDO v1.1

```
<!-- Without naming of rights holder -->
<lido:recordRights>
  <lido:rightsType>
    <skos:Concept rdf:about="https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/">
      <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="de">CC0 1.0 Universell</skos:prefLabel>
      <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="en">CC0 1.0 Universal</skos:prefLabel>
    </skos:Concept>
  </lido:rightsType>
</lido:recordRights>

<!-- With naming rights holder -->
<lido:recordRights>
  <lido:rightsType>
    <skos:Concept rdf:about="https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/4.0/">
      <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="de">CC BY-NC-SA 4.0 - Namensnennung-Nicht kommerziell 4.0 International</skos:prefLabel>
      <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="en">CC BY-NC-SA 4.0 - Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International</skos:prefLabel>
    </skos:Concept>
  </lido:rightsType>
  <lido:rightsHolder>
    <lido:legalBodyID lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00099" lido:source="ISIL (ISO 15511)">https://ld.zdb-services.de/resource/organisations/DE-MUS-031316</lido:legalBodyID>
    <lido:legalBodyName>
      <lido:appellationValue xml:lang="de">Schlesisches Museum zu Görlitz</lido:appellationValue>
      <lido:appellationValue xml:lang="en">Silesian Museum in Görlitz</lido:appellationValue>
    </lido:legalBodyName>
  </lido:rightsHolder>
</lido:recordRights>
```

Comparison with relevant standards and database models

Standard	Element name	Text/URI	Repeatable	Obligation level	Comment
German Digital Library: Metadata requirements for data provision	Rechtsstatus der Metadaten [eng.: Rights status of metadata]	URI	No	Mandatory	When contributing data to the German Digital Library , it is expected that the so-called core metadata (object information about the object) is not protected by copyright (CC0 1.0 Universal Public Domain Dedication).
German Digital Library LIDO application profile (DDB-LIDO)	<recordRights> / <rightsType> / <conceptID>	URI	No	Mandatory	Object description texts with a different legal status will be indicated in the <objectDescriptionRights> element in the DDB LIDO application profile .

CCC-LIDO Application profile	Legal status metadata <recordRights> / <rightsType> / <conceptID>	URI	No	Mandatory	
DFG Basic Data Record	Metadata Record Terms of Use	URI	Not specified	Mandatory	
DFG Practical Guidelines on Digitisation: LIDO core metadata	Dataset: <recordRights>	Text and/or URI	Yes	Mandatory if available	
Europeana Data Model (EDM)	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not mandatory	For datasets contributed to Europeana, the legal status of the metadata is expected to be in the public domain (Public Domain Mark or CC0 1.0 Universal)
EODEM application profile	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not mandatory	
Categories for the Description of Works of Art (2024)	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	
CDWA Lite (2006)	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	
Spectrum 5.1	Rights out reference number Rights out type	Text (controlled vocabulary) and URI	No	Not specified	The obligation level is determined by the institution.
digiCULT	Rechtsstatus der Metadaten [eng.: Rights status of metadata]	Text und URI	No	Mandatory	The licence is preset by default for every museum and is CC0 1.0 Universal in digiCULT .
museum-digital	Metadata rights (status)	Text (controlled vocabulary) and URI	No	Mandatory	The licence is preset by default for every museum and is CC BY-NC-SA in museum-digital , if no other license is selected.

ID data element

mds0024

Link to published metadata record (recommended)

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Definition

Persistent link to a presentation of the object which is publicly available on the web

Other possible database element names

Object in context

Permalink object

Source link

Text/URI

URI

Repeatable

Yes

Obligation level

Recommended

(Europeana: Mandatory)

Notes

In order to achieve sustainability according to the FAIR principles, the link must be persistent and lead to a publicly accessible object page on the web. Portals can use this link to allow their users to view the object/work in the collection's web database presentation.

Examples

https://sammlung-digital.lindenmuseum.de/de/objekt/kamm_6664

<https://ikmk.smb.museum/object?id=18237616>

Expression in LIDO (v1.0 and v1.1)

```
<lido:recordWrap>
  <lido:recordInfoSet>
    <lido:recordInfoLink xml:lang="de">https://sammlung-digital.lindenmuseum.de/de/objekt/kamm_6664</lido:
recordInfoLink>
  </lido:recordInfoSet>
</lido:recordWrap>
```

Comparison with relevant standards and database models

Standard	Element name	Text /URI	Repeatable	Obligation level	Comment
German Digital Library: Metadata requirements for data provision	Objekt im Kontext [eng.: Object in context]	URI	No	Conditionally mandatory (see comment)	For data contributions to the German Digital Library, a direct and persistent link to an online presentation of the object at the data provider is mandatory if there is no link to the media file or to the object in the media viewer .
German Digital Library LIDO application profile (DDB-LIDO)	<recordInfoSet> / <recordInfoLink>	URI	No	Conditionally mandatory (see comment)	Mandatory if <resourceSet> / <resourceRepresentation> / <linkResource> is not available In contrast to the Minimum Record Recommendation, this element may not be repeated in the DDB-LIDO application profile or in the CCC-LIDO application profile.
CCC-LIDO Application profile	Show original at data partner <recordInfoSet> / <recordInfoLink>	URI	No	Not mandatory	
DFG Basic Data Record	Source object: Additional information or context information	Text and/or URI	Yes	Recommended	The data element Source object: Additional information or context information in the DFG Basic Data Record may correspond to the link to the published metadata record, but other additional information may also be provided.
DFG Practical Guidelines on Digitisation: LIDO core metadata	Dataset: <recordInfoSet> / <recordInfoLink>	URI	Yes	Mandatory if available	
Europeana Data Model (EDM)	<ore:Aggregation> / <edm:isShownAt>	URI	No	Mandatory	
EODEM application profile	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	
Categories for the Description of Works of Art (2024)	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	
CDWA-lite (2006)	21.4.2 Record Info Link	Text	Yes	Not mandatory	
Spectrum 5.1	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	
digiCULT	<recordInfoSet> / <recordInfoLink>	URI	No	Not mandatory	
museum-digital	Web link	URI	No	Not applicable	

ID data element

mds0025

Record date (recommended)

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- [ID data element](#)

Definition

Export date of the record

Other possible database element names

Timestamp

Status of the information

Export date

Text/URI

Text (date format [ISO 8601](#) required)

Repeatable

No

Obligation level

Recommended

Notes

Dating of the data record in accordance with [ISO 8601](#) contributes to transparency and allows the timeliness of the information provided to be assessed. The export creation date should be provided. A modification date may be provided in a separate element, but must be clearly distinguishable from the export creation date.

Examples

2023-02-25

2015-09-01T17:21:05

Expression in LIDO (v1.0 and v1.1)

Note on the export creation date:

The type attribute of <lido:recordInfoSet> holds the value "<http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00470>" (LIDO record)

and

the type attribute of <lido:recordMetadataDate> holds the value "<http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00472>" (created)

```

<lido:recordWrap>
  <lido:recordInfoSet lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00470">
    <lido:recordMetadataDate lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00472">2015-09-01T17:
21:05</lido:recordMetadataDate>
  </lido:recordInfoSet>
</lido:recordWrap>

```

Comparison with relevant standards and database models

Standard	Element name	Text /URI	Repeatable	Obligation level	Comment
German Digital Library: Metadata requirements for data provision	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	
German Digital Library LIDO application profile (DDB-LIDO)	<recordInfoSet> / <recordMetadataDate>	Text (controlled format)	No	Recommended	The type attribute of <recordInfoSet> holds the value " http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00470 " (LIDO record) and the type attribute of <recordMetadataDate> holds the value " http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00472 " (created).
CCC-LIDO Application profile	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	
DFG Basic Data Record	Metadata Record Date	Text (controlled format)	No	Mandatory	
DFG Practical Guidelines on Digitisation : LIDO core metadata	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	
Europeana Data Model (EDM)	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	
EODEM application profile	Export Date /Timestamp	Text (controlled format)	No	Mandatory	
Categories for the Description of Works of Art (2024)	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	An export date is not provided in the CDWA , but a date for data record creation is: 25.5. Cataloging Date
CDWA Lite (2006)	(No match)	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	An export date is not provided in CDWA Lite , but a date for record creation or modification is: 21.4.5 Record Metadata Date
Spectrum 5.1	Recording date	Text (date format)	No	Recommended	Core element. The creation and each modification of the data record is documented in the change history. The obligation level is determined by the institution.
digiCULT	(No match)	Text (controlled format)	Yes	Mandatory	Various timestamps are generated automatically in digiCULT , including Metadata-Creation, Metadata-Modification, LIDO-Record-Modification.
museum-digital	Status of information	Text (controlled format)	Yes	Mandatory	The record is automatically dated when exported. Different archive versions can be created and retrieved.

ID data element

mds0026

FAQs (English)

Inhalt

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- [Who is the Minimum Record Recommendation for Museums and Collections intended for?](#)
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- [Why is an event mandatory in the object history? What if my database is not event-based?](#)
- [My object information is only available in German. Why do I need to indicate the language of the record?](#)
- [The objects I want to publish are to be catalogued within a specific discipline. Is the Minimum Record Recommendation still relevant to me?](#)
- [Why does the Minimum Record Recommendation suggest that my museum's object information should appeal to a wide audience?](#)
- [What does it mean when a software provider supports the Minimum Record Recommendation? Are there different levels?](#)
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- [Who can I contact if I have questions about using the Minimum Record Recommendation?](#)

What is the Minimum Record Recommendation for Museums and Collections?

The Minimum Record Recommendation specifies the most important data elements for the online publication of object information from museums and collections and provides information on how these elements should be filled in. The "minimum record" represents the smallest possible intersection of important data elements across most disciplines and museum types. In-depth cataloguing can build on this if required. The Recommendation ensures a minimum level of data quality and added value for users of the object information through compatibility with relevant standards and a focus on controlled vocabularies.

Who is the Minimum Record Recommendation for Museums and Collections intended for?

The Minimum Record Recommendation is aimed directly at museum staff, as well as museum consultants and those involved in education and training, who are active in communicating standards for online publication of object information. It is also explicitly aimed at database software providers. By incorporating the recommendation into their software products and services, they can ensure that the online publication of object data is technically supported in accordance with standards.

Who develops the Minimum Record Recommendation?

The Recommendation is being developed by the Minimum Record Working Group. It was initiated in 2022 by the Museum and Media Desks of the German Digital Library (DDB), the Working Group on Digitisation of the Konferenz der Museumsberatungsstellen in den Ländern (KMBL) and digiS Berlin. Members of the working group include representatives from the Institut für Museumsforschung - Staatliche Museen zu Berlin - Stiftung Preußischer Kulturbesitz, the Fachgruppe Dokumentation of the German Museum Association (DMB), the Coordination Centre for Scientific University Collections in Germany, digiCULT-Verbund eG, museum-digital Deutschland e. V., NFDI4Culture, NFDI4Objects, NFDI4Memory, Museum für Naturkunde Berlin and Übersee-Museum Bremen.

Both during the development of the beta version (2023) and the finalisation of the first full version of the Minimum Record Recommendation, which was published in May 2024, representatives from various stakeholder groups, including museum staff, persons working in consultancy and education, software providers and representatives from various cultural heritage portals, were involved and asked for feedback.

What are the objectives of the Recommendation?

The Minimum Record Recommendation is intended to pave the way for smaller and larger museums and collections to publish their data online and to communicate relevant standards in an easy-to-understand, low-threshold approach. The aim is to raise awareness of data quality in cultural institutions and support them with online publication. The recommendation is intended for practical application in everyday museum work.

The Minimum Record Recommendation is intended to support museums in setting the course for more consistent and higher-quality data right from the start. It assists them in gradually integrating controlled vocabularies into their documentation and publication practice, thus preparing their valuable datasets for up-to-date Linked Open Data scenarios.

What is the vision behind it?

The vision of the Minimum Record Recommendation for Museums and Collections is that data from museums can be linked beyond individual institutions and can be found and reused online by the widest possible audience, within the limits of the law. In this way, more people should become aware of and benefit from the work of museums in their leisure, school, work and research.

What are the application scenarios for the Minimum Record Recommendation?

Application scenarios for the Minimum Record Recommendation include the online publication of object information from museums and collections in online collections of individual institutions, but also the provision via cultural portals such as the German Digital Library and Europeana, as well as via data interfaces. The Recommendation is also intended to facilitate future integration into the [Culture Data Space](#) and the [Common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage](#). The Minimum Record Recommendation can support the preparation of object information for these scenarios.

What is new in version 1.0 compared to the beta version?

New features since the beta version include notes on digital accessibility, consideration of the needs of the natural history and numismatic communities, and advice on compliance with the CARE Principles. In addition, many examples have been added and, where appropriate, persistent URIs have been included. In addition to the [LIDO v1.0](#) snippets, [LIDO v1.1](#) snippets are now provided to explain the features of the data elements in the LIDO data exchange format.

Why is the Minimum Record Recommendation LIDO-compliant?

[LIDO](#) is a standard of the International Committee on Documentation of the International Council of Museums (ICOM CIDOC) for the publication of information on objects of material culture (see also [LIDO for cultural objects](#)). It is mainly developed by the German-speaking LIDO Working Group in the Documentation Section of the German Museums Association. LIDO is based on the CIDOC CRM ontology and allows objects to be described in a structured way using controlled vocabularies (see also [LIDO Primer](#)). Another feature of LIDO is that information about the history of an object is organised into individual events. As a data exchange format, LIDO is well suited for ensuring the interoperability or connectivity of object information, thus preparing datasets for Linked Open Data.

It has been shown that LIDO is not always easy to understand due to its language (XML-based) and structure (high degree of nesting, repeating element sets). In some cases, LIDO - a highly complex and flexible standard - exceeds the specific needs and capacities of museums and collections. The aim of the Minimum Record Recommendation is to take advantage of LIDO's benefits (structuring, controlled vocabulary integration, broad international acceptance) and to focus on the smallest possible intersection of data elements that are important for online publication across most disciplines and museum types. The explanation of the data elements in a generally comprehensible language and the integration of data element names from a large number of databases should make it easier to get started.

Why has the Minimum Record Recommendation not been mapped to EAD or MARC or METS /MODS?

The Minimum Record Recommendation focuses on the publication of object information from museums and collections. Objects from archives or libraries, even those affiliated with museums, are not included. Especially when publishing object information from museums, there is an increased need for guidance on standardised provision, which the Recommendation seeks to address.

Why is the Minimum Record Recommendation a LIDO application profile and what does it mean?

Application profiles define which components of LIDO must be included in a data record to meet the requirements of specific use cases (see also [LIDO training](#)). LIDO offers a large number of possible elements and attributes. In most use cases, some of these are not required and a selection is made as to which ones should be used.

Application profiles may be stricter than the [LIDO specification](#), but not more relaxed. If an element is mandatory in LIDO, it must also be mandatory in the application profiles. This also applies to the Minimum Record Recommendation. For example, the object title is mandatory in the Minimum Record Recommendation, just as it is in LIDO. In contrast to LIDO, the inventory number of the object is mandatory in the Minimum Record Recommendation because it is listed as an important data element in the relevant guidelines for museum cataloguing.

What is the purpose of the tables at the end of the data element pages?

The Minimum Record Recommendation is based on a comparison of the relevant standards for digital cataloguing and online publication of objects from museums and collections (including DFG [Basic Data Record](#), [DFG Practical Guidelines on Digitisation](#): LIDO core metadata, [Europeana Data Model](#)). The data element catalogues of the two federated databases digiCULT and museum-digital were also included. The resulting concordance can be found on the individual data element pages of the Minimum Record Recommendation.

With regard to (digital) cataloguing, the guidelines of the German Museum Association for basic cataloguing were taken into account ([Datenfeldkatalog zur Grundinventarisierung](#) [eng.: Data Element Catalogue for Basic Indexing] (1993), [Leitfaden für die Dokumentation von Museumsobjekten](#) [eng.: Guidelines for the Documentation of Museum Objects] (2011), [Digitale Grunderfassung. 10 Grundsätze](#) [eng.: Digital Basic Cataloguing. 10 Principles] (2022)). As the data element mentioned therein are not formally specified, these guidelines are not listed in the concordance tables.

What is the purpose of the LIDO snippets on the data element pages ("Expression in LIDO")?

The LIDO snippets (excerpts from a complete LIDO data record, expressed in so-called code blocks in XML language) show how the respective data element is translated into LIDO. This helps all those - museum staff or external service providers - who export data from the local database. Exporting in LIDO XML format is more suitable than in Excel or CSV format for making data available to portals or via data interfaces.

In addition to the LIDO snippets, the [Resources and Links](#) page provides a sample data record in Excel, CSV and XML formats that meets the requirements of the Minimum Record.

Why are the LIDO snippets shown in both LIDO v1.0 and LIDO v1.1?

LIDO was released in [version 1.0](#) in 2010 and in [version 1.1](#) in 2021. LIDO is backwards compatible. This means that records created in v1.0 will always be valid LIDO records. Version 1.1 offers helpful new features compared to version 1.0, e. g. controlled vocabularies can be integrated in a more differentiated way via the SKOS namespace and can be better analysed automatically. In the future, the German Digital Library will also be able to accept LIDO v1.1 data contributions. Since this is not yet the case, and since an important requirement of the Minimum Record Recommendation is that datasets conforming to the Minimum Record meet the requirements of the German Digital Library and Europeana, v1.0 snippets will be offered alongside v1.1 snippets, to support data contributions to the German Digital Library.

What does "Other possible database element names" mean?

In addition to the data element names used in the Minimum Record Recommendation, other common data element names are listed for each data element to illustrate the applicability of the Recommendation to cataloguing practice across the spectrum of the museum and collections landscape. The [Minimum Record Working Group](#) would be grateful for information about other common data element names that have not yet been included.

What is Linked Open Data? What is the role of controlled vocabularies here?

Linked Open Data (LOD) describes a network of data that originates from different sources - sources can be museum databases, for example - and is linked together. The public provision of data is crucial for linking. The data can be made available through data interfaces (these interfaces can be provided by the institutions themselves; cultural portals also usually offer different interfaces, e.g. OAI interfaces or APIs). The data must be provided in a machine-interpretable format (e.g. XML). In addition, URIs should be used wherever possible to identify terms. For example, in an LOD-compliant dataset, the object type or object designation should be described via a persistent link from a published controlled vocabulary. Suitable controlled vocabularies in this case are the [Art and Architecture Thesaurus](#), the [Integrated Authority File](#), [Wikidata](#) or the [Objektbezeichnungsdatei](#) [eng.: Object Designation File]. As an XML-based data exchange format, LIDO is ideal for publishing data for Linked Open Data.

What principles are the vocabulary recommendations on the element pages based on?

The Minimum Record Recommendation almost exclusively recommends controlled vocabularies that are suitable for various cultural heritage objects across disciplines and museum types as far as possible. The recommended vocabularies themselves comply with the guidelines of the FAIR principles: They have persistent identifiers in the form of URIs, are well documented and editorially maintained. They also contain clearly defined terms. The terms of use are clearly regulated by law. The vocabulary is equipped with a license that is as open as possible for machine evaluation. Some technical requirements must also be met: The vocabulary is available in certain machine-evaluable formats and is addressable via interfaces that are openly accessible on the Internet. There is also a whole range of terminologies that provide good content coverage of the documented objects in a subject-specific context. Even if such vocabularies are not explicitly mentioned in the Minimum Record Recommendation, they can be used if the FAIR criteria mentioned (largely) apply to them.

How do the FAIR Principles relate to the Minimum Record Recommendation?

The [FAIR Principles](#), published in 2016, promote making research data discoverable, accessible, interoperable and reusable. Object information from museums can be regarded as research data in that the recording and cataloguing of collection objects should follow scientifically standardised specifications and involves research activity. In addition, cataloguing information from museums provides important sources for research. As research is one of the pillars of museum work according to the ICOM Museum Definition, the FAIR Principles are also highly relevant to the work of museums in the context of digital transformation. The FAIR Principles should not be taken synonymous with the idea of open data. Rather, the FAIR Principles state that data should be made available as openly as possible and as closed as necessary (to meet legal requirements, for example). Nevertheless, the FAIR Principles provide important guidelines for the implementation of Linked Open Data. One aim of the Minimum Record Recommendation is to enable museums and collections to comply with the FAIR Principles in their publication practices and to make their object information available for Linked Open Data. Compatibility with the LIDO data format is an important step in this direction.

What role do the CARE Principles play in the Minimum Record Recommendation?

The [CARE Principles](#) (Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, Ethics) were formulated by the [Global Indigenous Data Alliance \(GIDA\)](#) for the management of indigenous data, as a necessary complementary framework to the FAIR Principles. GIDA aims to promote data sovereignty and governance. It aims to assert the rights and interests of people from communities of origin to the data for the purpose of self-determined well-being and to strengthen the right to participate in decision-making. The Minimum Record Recommendation provides cataloguing instructions for individual data elements with information on how to implement the CARE Principles. The notes are labelled on the following pages. The recommendations in the Minimum Record set refer to data on collection items from contexts of injustice, particularly colonial contexts. In order to ensure that the perspectives and positions of people from the countries where the objects originate are also taken into account, the CARE Principles should be followed. The most important thing is to involve people from the communities of origin in your own deliberations. More information can be found [here](#).

What role does digital accessibility play in the Minimum Record Recommendation?

Digital accessibility means that IT services can be used by people with physical or mental disabilities. The European Standard for Digital Accessibility [EN 301 549](#) is relevant here. Digital accessibility plays a role in the Minimum Record Recommendation because object datasets published online also represent IT content that must comply with the requirements of European and German legislation. It is also a declared aim of museums to reach as wide an audience as possible (see also the German Digital Library guidelines [Das inklusive Museum](#) [eng.: The inclusive museum] and [Standards für Museen](#) [eng.: Standards for museums] published by the German Museum Association, ICOM Germany and the KMBL). This includes museums' digital services. Information on digital accessibility is included in the Minimum Record Recommendation, for example in the Object description, Link to media file and Alternative texts data elements. Further information on the implementation of digital accessibility in museums can be found in [Einführung in die digitale Barrierefreiheit](#) [eng.: Introduction to digital accessibility] (video) or in the corresponding [portal](#) of the Landesstelle für die nichtstaatlichen Museen in Bayern [eng.: State Office for Non-Governmental Museums in Bavaria].

How is the Minimum Record Recommendation relevant to AI?

Thanks to LIDO compatibility, the Minimum Record Recommendation makes it possible to describe each museum object in a structured, contextual manner, using controlled vocabularies in a reliable and interoperable way. This improved data quality paves the way for appropriate subsequent use by AI applications in line with the curatorial needs of museums. Controlled cataloguing and comprehensive indexing is particularly helpful for the usability of cultural heritage data as datasets for training and improving large language models.

Does the Minimum Record Recommendation focus primarily on the cataloguing or publication of object information from museums and collections?

The Minimum Record Recommendation focuses on the online publication of object information from museums and collections. In order for object information to be findable, accessible, linkable and reusable according to the FAIR Principles, certain things need to be taken into account when it is recorded in local museum databases. In this respect, the data element pages of the Recommendation contain cataloguing instructions. However, the Minimum Record Recommendation is not primarily concerned with cataloguing, and certainly not with cataloguing for collection management purposes.

Why is the Data element set divided into "Data elements (cataloguing)" and "Data elements (export)"?

The data elements have been divided into two sections: Data elements that are usually filled in at the time of cataloguing ("Data elements (cataloguing)") and data elements that are usually filled in only when exporting from the database system used or when enriching the exported data ("Data elements (export)"). This is in line with museum workflows and is intended to separate contextual information, including media files, from formal information that does not normally require individual data entry but can be added at the point of export from the local system.

What about data elements that are important for digital collection management - why are they not included in the Minimum Record Recommendation?

Some of the data elements that are essential for good collection management, such as acquisition value or temporary location, must or should not be disclosed when object information is published online. The focus of the Minimum Record Recommendation is on the online publication of object information from museums and collections, so information used exclusively for collection management is excluded from the data element set.

Why so many data elements - shouldn't there be fewer for a Minimum Record?

A feature of the [LIDO data exchange format](#) is that descriptive object information is often provided both as a "human-readable" text element and as a "machine-readable" URI element containing unique identifiers in the form of persistent links. The Minimum Record Recommendation addresses this fact, which means that some data elements, such as the Person/corporate body element or the Repository of object element, actually represent multiple data elements, one text element and one URI element each. In addition, the Minimum Record Recommendation indicates when data elements or element sets should be repeatable. For best findability and reusability ([FAIR Principles](#)), not only well-structured object information with persistent URIs is required. In addition to the formal information about the object derived from cataloguing, a minimal amount of contextual information should be provided. For example, the Minimum Record Recommendation requires at least one event in the object's history and recommends the provision of a short, comprehensive object description text and subject keywords (if applicable). With regard to the description of the object, the Minimum Record Recommendation covers any information that users search for most frequently and that identifies the object in a relevant way. Finally, for provision in cultural heritage portals, certain information that is taken for granted in the local context and is part of common institutional knowledge needs to be made explicit.

Why are the requirements of the German Digital Library (DDB) and Europeana portals mentioned several times?

In addition to the consideration of standards and data element sets in the creation of the Minimum Record Recommendation, the coverage of the mandatory data elements for participation in the portals [German Digital Library](#) and [Europeana](#) was crucial. If the object data are prepared according to the Minimum Record Recommendation, all data-related requirements of these two portals are fulfilled and the way is paved for contributing. It is because of this requirement that some data elements are marked as *mandatory* in the Minimum Record Recommendation.

As the Recommendation aims to be as easily understandable and accessible as possible, it uses limited technical jargon and IT terminology. To ensure compatibility with [LIDO \(Lightweight Information Describing Objects\)](#), the data ingest format used by the German Digital Library, LIDO snippets are provided for each data element. It is not necessary to read these to understand the data elements.

What if I do not plan to submit data to the DDB and Europeana? Is the Minimum Record Recommendation still relevant for me/my institution?

The Minimum Record Recommendation is intended to meet the requirements of the German Digital Library and Europeana portals so that datasets that comply with the Minimum Record Recommendation can be delivered to these portals as smoothly as possible. However, this is not the only intended benefit of the Minimum Record Recommendation. In a broader sense, the Minimum Record Recommendation serves to improve the data quality of published object information from museums and collections, regardless of the platforms or interfaces used.

Other subject-specific portals or the online collections of individual institutions often set similar priorities to the German Digital Library and Europeana in terms of search access to the objects presented. Even when data is provided directly via interfaces, users benefit from the consistent provision of core object information in a well-documented format. The Minimum Record Recommendation is therefore a good starting point for any form of publication of these data.

Why is an event mandatory in the object history? What if my database is not event-based?

One of the claims of the Minimum Record Recommendation is that, in addition to strictly formal requirements for the online publication of object information from museums and collections, a minimal amount of contextualising information should be provided. For example, in order for users to make sense of the object data, the object needs to be located in space and time. As the Minimum Record Recommendation is [LIDO-compliant](#), information about what happened to the object (event type), who was involved (person/corporate body), where (location) and when (date) it took place must be structured into events. If the institution does not know any of this information about an object, it should at least be possible to specify a time period for the creation of the object or its entry into the collection and thus create an event. Any number of events can be assigned to an object.

If the database does not support event-based recording, it is still possible to transfer information that belongs into a LIDO event. For example, when exporting data from the local database, event types are defined based on the role of the actor (creator, seller, etc.) and the information on the person /corporate body, location and date is assigned to a corresponding event.

My object information is only available in German. Why do I need to indicate the language of the record?

A feature of the LIDO data exchange format is that the language of the object information must be specified at least at the general record level. In order to achieve LIDO compatibility, the Record language element is mandatory in the Minimum Record Recommendation. The data element must be filled even if the object information is only available in one language, e. g. German.

In LIDO it is also possible to repeat data elements in order to publish the object information in different languages. To do this, the individual data element contents are labelled with their own language.

The objects I want to publish are to be catalogued within a specific discipline. Is the Minimum Record Recommendation still relevant to me?

The Minimum Record Recommendation aims to provide an intersection of important data elements for online publication across disciplines and museum types. For example, the requirements of cultural history collections have been considered alongside those of natural history collections. The Minimum Record is intended to provide a core of data elements on which more detailed cataloguing can be based if desired. For more detailed cataloguing, the LIDO data exchange format offers a wealth of additional data elements that are not included in the Minimum Record Recommendation or that are only referred to in a few places (for example, in the Date element, it is indicated that information on the period or epoch is permitted in a separate data element corresponding to the LIDO element `<lido:periodName>`). However, even very specific types of objects or works can often be processed well according to the Minimum Record Recommendation if you use the appropriate published specialist vocabularies. If you are missing basic requirements for cataloguing and online publication in your discipline in the Minimum Record Recommendation, please contact the [Minimum Record Working Group](#).

Why does the Minimum Record Recommendation suggest that my museum's object information should appeal to a wide audience?

It is a declared aim of museums to appeal to as wide an audience as possible. In the ICOM 2022 museum definition, museums are described as "accessible and inclusive" (see the corresponding [communication](#) from ICOM Germany; see also the [Standards for museums](#) published by the German Museum Association, ICOM Germany and KMBL). This also means that the digital services provided by museums, including object data published online, should be presented as generally understandable as possible.

What does it mean when a software provider supports the Minimum Record Recommendation? Are there different levels?

The leading providers of database software for museums and collections in Germany, Austria and Switzerland have been consulted several times (beta version 2023 and 1.0 version 2024) as part of the work on the Minimum Record Recommendation. Many of them have now declared their support for the Minimum Record Recommendation. This means that a data export compliant to the Minimum Record is possible with the database software they provide. In addition, there are nuances in the sense that, for example, some databases already inform their users at the time of cataloguing which data elements are mandatory and which are recommended for compliance with the Minimum Record Recommendation. A list of software providers that support the Minimum Record Recommendation can be found [here](#). If you have any questions about the extent to which your database provider technically supports the Minimum Record Recommendation, please contact them directly.

When I enter data into my museum database, will I receive information on which data elements are mandatory/recommended and how they should be filled in?

Some providers of museum and collections database software that support the Minimum Record Recommendation (a list of software providers can be found [here](#)) already inform their users at the time of data entry which elements are mandatory and which are recommended in order to comply with the Recommendation. It would also be helpful if, in addition to the mandatory nature of the data elements, the databases included the data entry instructions of the Minimum Record Recommendation in their software products. If you would like to see this feature, please contact your database provider.

Who can I contact if I have questions about using the Minimum Record Recommendation?

For further support in using the Minimum Record Recommendation, including filling in the data elements and using controlled vocabularies, please contact the [Museumsberatungsstellen](#) [eng.: museum advice centres] in your federal state, the [Museum](#) and [Media](#) Desks of the German Digital Library, the NFDI4Culture [Helpdesk](#) or your database provider. You can also send questions to the Minimum Record Working Group at info@minimaldatensatz.de.

Resources and Links

Inhalt

- [Example data record](#)
- [Presentation](#)
- [Poster](#)
- [Mapping table](#)
- [FAIR Principles](#)
- [digiS LIDO-Validator \(BETA\)](#)
- [XML Schema](#)
- [List of software providers and cooperatives](#)
- [Publications](#)

Example data record

The example data record is intended for museum and collection staff or external service providers who are preparing to export data from the local database. It serves to illustrate how the respective data elements of the Minimum Record Recommendation for Museums and Collections are translated into LIDO-XML. To enable low-threshold access for export creation, a CSV mapping table with the data fields is also provided.

XML: [Example_Record_MKG_LIDO_1.0.xml](#), [Example_Record_MKG_LIDO_1.1.xml](#)

CSV/XSLX: [Example_Record_MKG.csv](#), [Example_Record_MKG.xlsx](#)

The example data record is also made available in a Git repository: <https://github.com/AG-Minimaldatensatz/Musterdatensatz.github>

Presentation

Minimaldatensatz-Empfehlung für Museen und Sammlungen (Beta-Version): Eine Einführung. [eng.: Minimum Record Recommendation (beta version): An introduction; in German]: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10391796>

Minimaldatensatz-Empfehlung für Museen und Sammlungen (Beta-Version): Eine Einführung. [eng.: Minimum Record Recommendation (v.1.0.1): An introduction; in German]: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13911937>

Poster

Minimaldatensatz-Empfehlung für Museen und Sammlungen (Beta-Version). [eng.: Minimum Record Recommendation (beta version, in German)]: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10210766>

Minimum Record Recommendation for Museums and Collections (v.1.0.1). Posterpräsentation auf der UMAC/UNIVERSEUM-Tagung Dresden: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13577911>

Minimaldatensatz-Empfehlung für Museen und Sammlungen. Posterpräsentation auf dem NFDI4Objects Community Meeting 2024: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13771750>

Mapping table

[LIDO v1.1 Mapping table, incl. application profile of Minimal Record Recommendation v1.0.1](#)

FAIR Principles

Go Fair Initiative: FAIR Principles - <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

Kailus, Angela: Handreichung für ein FAIRes Management kulturwissenschaftlicher Forschungsdaten. In: NFDI4Culture Guidelines - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7716941> and <https://nfdi4culture.de/go/E3625>.

Marchini, Chiara: Der Blick über den Tellerrand. Rezeption der FAIR-Prinzipien an Museen in Deutschland. 2024 - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12651729>.

RDA FAIR data maturity model Working Group: Das FAIR Data Maturity Model. Spezifikation und Leitlinien. 2020. CC BY 4.0 - <https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00050>.

Wilkinson, Mark et al.: The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. In: Scientific Data 3, (2016), Artikelnr.: 160018 - <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>.

CARE Principles

The Global Indigenous Data Alliance: CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance - <https://www.gida-global.org/care>

The Global Indigenous Data Alliance - Research Data Alliance International Indigenous Data Sovereignty Interest Group: CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance. 2019 - https://static1.squarespace.com/static/5d3799de845604000199cd24/t/6397b363b502ff481fce6baf/1670886246948/CARE%2BPrinciples_One%2BPagers%2BFINAL_Oct_17_2019.pdf

Local Contexts, Inc.: Grounding Indigenous Rights - <https://localcontexts.org/>

Imeri, S., & Rizzolli, M.: CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance: Eine Leitlinie für ethische Fragen im Umgang mit Forschungsdaten?. In: O-Bib. Das Offene Bibliotheksjournal Herausgeber VDB, 9,2 (2022), S. 1-14 - <https://doi.org/10.5282/o-bib/5815>

digis LIDO-Validator (BETA)

<https://www.digis-berlin.de/diliva/>

The diLIVA LIDO-Validator by digiS is used to check LIDO XML data against the specifications from the minimum data set recommendation version 1.0 and 1.0.1. The validator is still under active development.

If you have any questions, comments or suggestions, please contact [Alexander Winkler \(winkler@zib.de\)](mailto:winkler@zib.de) or [Marco Klindt \(klindt@zib.de\)](mailto:klindt@zib.de).

XML Schema

A schema file (XSD) for checking the specifications from the minimum data set recommendation v1.0.1 for LIDO XML data is available here: <https://www.digis-berlin.de/diliva/static/lido-v1.1-profile-minimumrecordrecommendation-v1.0.1.xsd> (Download).

List of software providers and cooperatives

The databases of the following providers and cooperatives support the Minimum Record Recommendation:

	Software provider or cooperative	Database	Notes on application of the Minimum Record Recommendation
1	Axiell	Axiell Collections	
2	CD-Lab Bonn	VINO (=Virtual INternet Objects)	
3	digiCULT-Verbund eG	digiCULT.web	
4	Förderverein des Freilichtmuseums am Kiekeberg e. V.	FirstRumos museum software	
5	Germanisches Nationalmuseum Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg Museum Koenig Bonn Interessengemeinschaft für semantische Datenverarbeitung e. V.	WissKI	CIDOC CRM based data model for Minimum Record Recommendation (WissKI Pathbuilder)
6	Joanneum Research	imdas pro	
7	museum-digital Deutschland e. V.	museum-digital	museum-digital:handbuch annotated PDF
8	Robotron Datenbank-Software GmbH	robotron*Daphne	
9	Verbundzentrale des GBV	kuniweb and naniweb	
10	zetcom	MuseumPlus	

Publications

The Minimum Record Recommendation is discussed in the following publications:

- Marchini, C.; Städtler, D.; McNeilly, N.: Europeana Impact Playbook helps to develop recommendations for cultural heritage metadata, 2024.
Blog-Beitrag: <https://pro.europeana.eu/post/europeana-impact-playbook-helps-to-develop-recommendations-for-cultural-heritage-metadata>
- Gerber, A.; Städtler, D.: Die Minimaldatensatz-Empfehlung für archäologische Forschungsdaten, in: Archäologische Informationen 47, 2025.
Open Access: https://dguf.de/fileadmin/AI/archinf-ev_staedtler_gerber.pdf
- Kailus, A.; Götsch, S.: The Minimum Record Recommendation for Museums and Collections. Conference Proceedings EVA Berlin 2025 (in print)

Change log (English)

• v.1.1 (2025-10-02)

- Minor adjustments on [Recommendation start page](#): Logos of the participating institutions
- Minor corrections on the data element pages
 - Addition of code blocks "Expression in LIDO"
 - [Event in object history](#): Code block for LIDO v.1.1
 - [Measurements](#): Code block for LIDO v.1.1 for event-dependent dimensions
 - [Materials](#) and [Techniques](#): Code block for LIDO v.1.1 for event-independent material/technology information
 - Precise wording of cataloguing notes
 - [Record language](#): Rewording of the cataloguing note including a discussion of the case 'Language of the object or work'
- The following standards were added to the concordance table ("Comparison with relevant standards and database models")
 - Application profile CCC-LIDO
 - [Categories for the Description of Works of Art](#) (2024)
 - [CDWA Lite](#) (2006)
 - [Spectrum](#)
- Update of [FAQs](#) page
- Update of [Resources and Links & Credits and Citation](#) page
 - Addition of posters
 - Addition of a short bibliography FAIR Principles
 - Update of the short bibliography CARE Principles
 - Addition of XML Schema
 - Addition of Publications
- Update of [Credits and Citation](#) page
 - Update of the people involved in the Working Group
 - Alignment of the Citation Note with Zenodo version

v.1.0.1 (2024-01-11)

- Obligation level is added in brackets after the data element names, so it will appear in the data element catalogue on the start page, on the data element pages and in the navigation bar
- Minor adjustments on the [Recommendation start page](#): logos of participating institutions; newsletter registration
- Minor corrections on the data element pages
 - Precise wording of recording notes: [Object description](#) and [Link to published metadata record](#)
 - Code block "Expression in LIDO": [Institution providing record](#)
- Corrections, changes and additions to [Resources and Links](#):
 - Update of example data record (XML and CSV/XLSX)
 - [digiS LIDO validator](#) (beta) linked
 - Update of the mapping table from Lido 1.1 to the data elements of the Minimum Record Recommendation
 - PDF with information on the use of a CIDOC CRM-based data model for the Minimum Record Recommendation (WissKI Pathbuilder)
- Update of [Credits and Citation](#) page

Credits and Citation

Minimum Record Working Group

As part of the Minimum Record Working Group, the following persons have been involved in the development of the current version of the Minimum Record Recommendation:

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Wiki: www.minimaldatensatz.de

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1	Arbeitsstelle für Standardisierung, German National Library	Barbara Pfeifer
2	Arbeitsstelle für Standardisierung, German National Library	Chantal Köppl
3	Arbeitsstelle für Standardisierung, German National Library	Mathias Manecke
4	Arbeitsstelle für Standardisierung, German National Library	Sarah Hartmann
5	Arbeitsstelle für Standardisierung, German National Library	Barbara Fischer
6	Architekturmuseum, Technische Universität Berlin	Dr. Hans-Dieter Nägelke
7	Axiell ALM Germany GmbH	Dirk Witthaut
8	Axiell ALM Germany GmbH	Rene van den Heuvel
9	Badisches Landesmuseum	Mario Lampe
10	CD-Lab Bonn (VINO)	Ulrich Gloede
11	Coordination Centre for Scientific University Collections in Germany	Sarah Elena Link
12	Corpus Nummorum, Berlin-Brandenburgische Akademie der Wissenschaften	Dr. Ulrike Peter
13	Corpus Nummorum, Berlin-Brandenburgische Akademie der Wissenschaften	PD Dr. Vladimir Stolba
14	Deutsche Fotothek - Sächsische Landesbibliothek - Staats- und Universitätsbibliothek Dresden	Dr. Jens Bove
15	Deutsche Fotothek - Sächsische Landesbibliothek - Staats- und Universitätsbibliothek Dresden	Dr. Simone Fleischer
16	Deutsches Dokumentationszentrum für Kunstgeschichte, Bildarchiv Foto-Marburg, Philipps-Universität Marburg	Christian Bracht
17	Deutsches Dokumentationszentrum für Kunstgeschichte, Bildarchiv Foto-Marburg, Philipps-Universität Marburg	Dr. Gudrun Knaus
18	Deutsches Dokumentationszentrum für Kunstgeschichte, Bildarchiv Foto-Marburg, Philipps-Universität Marburg	Klaus Bulle
19	Digitales Kunst- und Kulturarchiv Düsseldorf (d:kult)	Tamara Tolnai
20	Ethnologisches Museum und Museum für Asiatische Kunst, Staatliche Museen zu Berlin	Anna Seidel
21	Europeana	Henning Scholz
22	Förderverein des Freilichtmuseums am Kiekeberg e. V. (FirstRumos Museumsoftware)	Lars Steinberg
23	Forschungs- und Kompetenzzentrum Digitalisierung Berlin (digiS)	Marco Klindt
24	Freilichtmuseum Roscheider Hof	Helge Klaus Rieder
25	German Digital Library, Head Office	Dr. Julia Spohr
26	German Digital Library, Service Desk & Data Management	Claudia Effenberger
27	German Digital Library, Service Desk & Data Management	Denise Baumgart
28	German Digital Library, Service Desk & Data Management	Eleonore Emsbach
29	German Digital Library, Service Desk & Data Management	Jennifer Treu
30	Germanisches Nationalmuseum	Robert Nasarek
31	Göttingen State and University Library	Barbara Fichtl
32	Göttingen State and University Library	Timo Schleier
33	Heidelberg University Library, heidICON	Nicole Sobriel
34	Herder Institute for Historical Research on East Central Europe	Felix Köther

35	Hochschule für Technik und Wirtschaft Berlin	Prof. Dr. Dorothee Haffner
36	Humboldt-Universität, Mediathek - Bildsammlungen des Instituts für Kunst- und Bildgeschichte	Dr. Georg Schelbert
37	Institut für Museumsforschung	Kathrin Grotz
38	Institut für Museumsforschung	Prof. Dr. Patricia Rahemipour
39	Joanneum Research (Imdas Pro)	Silvia Russegger
40	Joanneum Research (Imdas Pro)	Werner Preininger
41	Jüdisches Museum Frankfurt	Sonja Thäder
42	Landesmuseum Württemberg	Hanna Warth-Geraci
43	Landesmuseum Württemberg	Noreen Klingspor
44	LEO-BW	Jens Lill
45	mindscreen GmbH	Annett Farnetani
46	Münzkabinett Berlin	Dr. Angela Berthold
47	Museum für Naturkunde, Berlin	Mareike Petersen
48	Museum für russlanddeutsche Kulturgeschichte, Detmold	Nico Wiethof
49	Museum Wiesbaden	PD Dr. Thomas Hörnschemeyer
50	museum-digital Deutschland e. V.	Joshua Enslin
51	Museumsverband Hessen	Bettina von Andrian (freiberuflich)
52	Museumsverband Hessen	Hauer und Krause (freiberuflich)
53	MusIS-Verbund	Dr. Werner Schweibenz
54	The National Gallery, London	Rupert Shepherd
55	Pausanio GmbH & Co.KG	Prof. Dr. Holger Simon
56	Programmfabrik GmbH (EasyDB)	Sebastian Klarmann
57	Robotron Datenbank-Software GmbH (robotron*Daphne)	Ulrich Servos
58	Saarländischer Museumsverband	Sabine Geith
59	Sächsische Landesstelle für Museumswesen	Johanna Jürgens
60	Sammlungsdinge	Patrick McDonough
61	Solvatec (BeeCollect)	
62	Städtische Museen Freiburg	Jochen Dietel
63	Stiftung für Kunst, Kultur und Geschichte, Winterthur	Sonja Gasser
64	Stiftung Historischer Museen Hamburg	Doreen Wand
65	zetcom Informatikdienstleistungs AG (MuseumPlus)	Jette Klein-Berning